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This report describes the minimum acceptable injection energy into the booster, the lattice concept together with a workable beam optics, the ramp strategy, and the top-up injection into the collider.

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Deliverable 2.3: Full-energy booster design

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Abstract

This report describes the minimum acceptable injection energy into the booster, the lattice concept together with a workable beam optics, the ramp strategy, and the top-up injection into the collider.

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1 Booster summary

1.1 The booster in the whole injection complex

The baseline of the injector complex in the CDR [1] uses an electron linac producing up to 2 electron bunches of 5 nC with a maximum repetition rate of 200 Hz (for the Z operation) and going down to 50 Hz for $t\bar{t}$ and an energy of 1.54 GeV. Under recommendation of the mid-term review, an alternative is to produce up to 4 bunches at one and accelerate them in a linac with repetition frequency of 100 Hz for the Z and W operations. The electron beam is then accelerated in a common linac for the electrons and positrons up to 6 GeV. At this point, the electron beam can be transported up to a positron target to produce a positron beam or to a high-energy linac to be accelerated up to 20 GeV. When converted to a positron beam, the latter is accelerated in a positron linac up to 1.54 GeV, damped in a low-energy damping ring, transported up to the entrance of the common linac to be accelerated again up to 6 GeV, and accelerated in the high-energy linac up to 20 GeV. In both cases, the 20 GeV beam is then transported up to the booster. A schematic layout of the whole injector complex is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Schematic layout of Injector complex.

An alternative scheme is under investigation as shown in Fig. 2. In this scheme, we have an electron source and an electron linac accelerating the beam up to 2.86 GeV. Then, the electron beam is alternatively sent to a converter target to positrons, which are then accelerated in a positron linac up to 2.86 GeV, or directly transported to a high-energy damping ring. After damping, the electron or positron beam is then accelerated up to 20 GeV.

1.2 From the booster to the collider

The booster continuously performs a top-up injection into the collider. The reason is to keep the imbalance between the bunch population of the colliding electron-positron beams within the range ± 5 % for the Z -mode and within the range ± 3 % for the three other modes. For larger imbalance, we excite the bootstrapping instability [2]. The beam lifetime in the collider with 4 IPs is respectively for the Z , W , ZH and $t\bar{t}$ modes 868.1 s, 492.4 s, 376.2 s and 348.2 s. By taking into account the maximum allowed imbalance between the two colliding beams, the target for the

Fig. 2: Alternative layout of Injector complex by using a high-energy damping ring.

interval between the top-up injection of the e^+ and e^- beams is for the 4 modes 43.4s, 14.8s, 11.3s and 10.4s. The main parameters of the collider are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: FCC-ee collider parameters as of July 30, 2023

Value	Unit	Z	WW	ZH	$t\bar{t}$
Beam energy	[GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Layout			PA31-3.0		
Number of IPs			4		
Circumference	[km]		90.658816		
Bend. radius of arc dipole	[km]		10.021		
Energy loss / turn	[GeV]	0.0391	0.374	1.88	10.29
SR power / beam	[MW]		50		
Beam current	[mA]	1279	137	26.7	4.9
Colliding bunches / beam		11200	1780	380	56
Colliding bunch population	10^{11}	2.14	1.45	1.32	1.64
Hor. emittance at collision ϵ_x	[nm]	0.71	2.17	0.67	1.57
Ver. emittance at collision ϵ_y	[pm]	1.9	2.2	1.0	1.6
Lattice ver. emittance $\epsilon_{y,lattice}$	[pm]	0.85	1.25	0.65	1.1
Arc cell		Long 90/90		90/90	
Momentum compaction α_p	10^{-6}		28.6		7.4
Arc sext families			75		146
$\beta_{x/y}^*$	[mm]	110/0.7	220/1	240/1	800/1.5
Hor. tune Q_x		218.158	218.185	398.192	398.148
Ver. tune Q_y		222.200	222.220	398.360	398.216
Hor. Chromaticity Q'_x		0	0	0	0
Ver. Chromaticity Q'_y		5	2	0	0
Energy spread (SR/BS) σ_δ	[%]	0.039/0.109	0.070/0.109	0.103/0.152	0.159/0.201
Bunch length (SR/BS) σ_z	[mm]	5.60/15.5	3.46/5.09	3.40/5.09	1.85/2.33
RF voltage 400/800 MHz	[GV]	0.079/0	1.00/0	2.08/0	2.1/9.38
Harm. number for 400 MHz			121 200		
RF frequency (400 MHz)	[MHz]		400.786 684		
Synchrotron tune Q_s		0.0288	0.081	0.032	0.089
Long. damping time	[turns]	1158	219	64	18.3
RF acceptance	[%]	1.05	1.15	1.8	3.1
Energy acceptance (DA)	[%]	± 1.0	± 1.0	± 1.6	-2.8/+2.5
Beam crossing angle at IP	[mrad]		± 15		
Crab waist ratio	[%]	70	55	50	40
Beam-beam ξ_x/ξ_y^a		0.0022/0.097	0.013/0.128	0.010/0.088	0.066/0.144
Piwinski angle ($\theta_x\sigma_z, BS$)		26.4	3.7	5.4	0.99
Lifetime (q + BS + lattice)	[s]	10 000	4000	3500	3000
Lifetime (lum) ^b	[s]	1330	970	660	650
Luminosity / IP	$[10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}]$	141	20	6.3	1.38
Luminosity / IP (CDR)	$[10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}]$	230	28	8.5	1.8

^a incl. hourglass.

^b only the energy acceptance is taken into account for the cross section.

Particle tracking simulations have been performed using SAD+BBWS for the main ring [3] and with the z-pole lattice (45.6 GeV columns in Table 1) by considering a beam size of $n_R = 4$ RMS of the stored beam, $n_I = 4$ RMS of the injected beam, and a septum thickness of $w = 3$ mm. The tracking includes the lattice, synchrotron radiation, tapering, crab-waist, weak-strong beam-beam, and beamstrahlung. No vertical excitation in the ring is applied. The loss of the injected beam is observed up to 4000 turns after the injection, which corresponds to about twice the transverse damping time. Even with high emittances, the expected loss at the injection is about 11 %, which is half of the total loss budget (see Fig. 3). Further fine tuning stays possible on n_I , or n_R . The Table 2 summarizes the injection efficiency from the booster to the collider. From these studies, we can conclude that we should aim at horizontal emittances as small as in the collider. Up to a factor 5 should be acceptable for the vertical emittance with no significant impact on the loss level, corresponding to a maximum allowed vertical emittance of 9.5 pm. The studies on the injection into the collider have shown that the losses are little sensitive to a mismatching on the bunch length. That is why the longitudinal parameters at the extraction from the booster are now optimized for the energy acceptance and power consumption rather than for longitudinal matching with the collider.

Fig. 3: Injection efficiency from the booster to the collider by tracking (lattice+beam-beam+beamstrahlung) for different ratios between the beam emittance at the exit of the booster $\epsilon_{(x,y)I}$ and of the stored beam in the collider $\epsilon_{(x,y)R}$.

Table 2: Injection efficiency for different ratios between the beam emittance at the exit of the booster and the emittance of the stored beam in the collider.

$\epsilon_{xI}/\epsilon_{xR}$	$\epsilon_{yI}/\epsilon_{yR}$	Injection efficiency (%)
1	1	98.6
1	5	97
5	5	88.6

1.3 Booster parameters

The booster is mostly located in the same tunnel as the collider. To simplify the mechanical integration of the booster, the length of one arc cell is 52 m, equal to the one of the short cell in the collider. More precisely, the arc periodicity is equal to 5 short cells because of the non-interleaved sextupole scheme. However, the layout of the booster (see Fig. 4) presents some differences with the collider one. These differences are listed below and emphasized in Fig. 5:

- The beam in the booster should run at 8 m in the outer side from the interaction point to avoid any perturbation induced by the synchrotron radiation from the booster to the collision point.
- The booster beam pipe is located on the top level of the tunnel with a vertical offset of 1030 mm and a horizontal offset currently equal to 161 mm towards the inner side. This offset is to enable to get exactly the same circumference between the collider and the booster. The cells of the booster have also a longitudinal offset to improve the mechanical stability and integration of the tunnel section. Since the patterns of the arc cells of the booster and collider are slightly different, we have an oscillation of the distance between the two reference trajectories of about ± 4 mm. This orbit variation also depends on the dipoles patterns in the arcs.
- The RF cavities are located in the long straight section H whereas the ones of the collider are located in section L.

Fig. 4: Layout of the booster and collider. The booster shares the tunnel with the collider. The RF cavities of the booster are located in point L.

The parameters for the booster are summarized in Table 3.

2 Optics

2.1 Main constraints

In the CDR [1], two optics were developed: the Z/W and $ZH/t\bar{t}$ modes respectively using a FODO arc cell with a phase advance of 60° and 90° , respectively. The main reason for a different

Fig. 5: Layout of the booster and collider in the section A, left. The distance between the reference axis of the booster and collider arcs is shown on the right picture.

Table 3: Preliminary key parameters of the high-energy booster of FCC-ee. We consider here a linac of 20 GeV as a pre-injector.

Running mode		Z	W	ZH	$t\bar{t}$
Circumference	[km]		90.658745		
Injection energy	[GeV]	20			
Extraction energy	[GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Number booster ramps per cycle		10	2	1	1
Number of stored bunches		1120	890	380	56
Particle number/bunch (filling)	$[10^{10}]$	2.5	2.5	1	1
Particle number/bunch (top-up)	$[10^{10}]$	2.14	0.87	0.792	0.984
Collider top-up interval	[s]	43.405	14.772	11.286	10.446
RF frequency	[MHz]	800			
Lattice version		V24_FODO			
Momentum compaction		7.12×10^{-6}			
Coupling		2×10^{-3}			
Injection emittances (norm.)	[μm]	10×10			
Extraction horizontal equilibrium emittance	[nm]	0.087	0.27	0.61	1.4
Extraction vertical equilibrium emittance	[pm]	0.175	0.537	1.21	2.80
Injection Energy loss / turn	[MeV]	1.34			
Extraction Energy loss / turn	[MeV]	36.1	342	1730	9270
Injection bunch length	[mm]	4			
Extraction bunch length	[mm]	4.38	3.55	3.34	1.94
Injection RMS energy spread	$[10^{-3}]$	1			
Extraction RMS energy spread	$[10^{-3}]$	0.38	0.67	1.01	1.53
Injection Maximum relative energy acceptance	[%]	3			
Extraction Maximum relative energy acceptance	[%]	1	1.01	1.51	2.29
Injection RF voltage	[MV]	50.1			
Extraction RF voltage	[MV]	57.2	402	1960	10200
Filling time	[s]	2.8	4.45	3.8	0.56
Up-Ramp time	[s]	0.706	0.75	1.25	2.03125
Flat top	[s]	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Down-Ramp time	[s]	0.334	0.75	1.25	2.03125
Total cycling time	[s]	39.4	12.1	6.4	4.7225

phase advance was to get a larger momentum compaction for the Z/W modes to mitigate the TCBI (Transverse Coupled Bunch Instabilities) at injection. However, the work performed since the CDR has also shown that the TMCI (Transverse Mode Coupling Instabilities) may drive the maximum allowed bunch charge.

Concerning the $ZH/t\bar{t}$ modes, the TCBI is not an issue because of a much smaller average current. That is not the case for the TMCI because of a large bunch charge (4 nC) during the collider filling. The studies on the filling scheme have shown that a bunch charge of 4 nC is not mandatory for all the operations: we can have a bunch charge of 1.6 nC (still larger than the

minimum bunch charge to mitigate the bootstrapping instability) with a negligible impact on the filling time of the collider for the $ZH/t\bar{t}$ modes.

Concerning the Z/W modes, the studies on the collective effects have shown that the main driver of the TMCI is the beam pipe. To manage a bunch charge of 4 nC, two approaches were investigated: going to a larger momentum compaction or going to a smaller transverse impedance. Going to a larger momentum compaction implies a larger equilibrium emittance, a different optics for the different operation modes, and additional magnet families to operate the booster with different working points as it is the case for the collider. Going to a smaller transverse impedance means to reduce the contribution of the beam pipe. The proposed solution is to consider a beam pipe made from copper or based on copper-coated stainless steel, and to enlarge the inner diameter of the beam pipe from 50 mm to 60 mm. The studies have shown that going to a larger diameter than 60 mm will result in a significant increase of the magnet costs. A diameter of 60 mm looked like a good compromise between bigger and heavier magnets and a smaller transverse impedance.

Finally, the reduction by a factor 10 of the stored current in the booster significantly reduces the constraints linked to the TCBI and thus to require a large momentum compaction. In conclusion, the current strategy is to use the same optics for all operation modes. The retained solution to keep the same optics for all modes was to enlarge the inner diameter of the vacuum chamber.

The beam stability in the booster requires to correct the chromaticity, and thus to use sextupoles. The CDR has compared three different sextupole schemes; the sextupoles that are separated by a phase advance of π form a family:

- Interleaved sextupole scheme. After every quadrupole a sextupole magnet is installed leading to a maximum number of sextupoles. In this case there are two families per plane.
- Non-interleaved sextupole scheme. The sextupoles are considered to only act in one plane and are interlaced with the ones of the other plane.
- Completely non-interleaved sextupole scheme. In order to optimise the cancellation of the sextupole's geometric effect, only linear elements are installed between two sextupoles forming a pair.

The studies in the CDR have shown that the configuration with the completely non-interleaved sextupole scheme gives the best dynamic aperture and momentum acceptance. We have kept this sextupole scheme. To go further in the momentum acceptance, we have also added some transparency conditions on the dispersion suppressors and insertions to match the chromatic functions:

- The phase advance between the focusing sextupoles in the dispersion suppressor is π in both planes to maximize the geometric aberration cancellation.
- The angles of some dipoles in the dispersion suppressors have been matched to cancel the second-order dispersion. However, the total angle of the dispersion suppressor stays unchanged.
- The phase advance between the end of the left arc (or the beginning of the left dispersion suppressor) and the beginning of the right arc (or the start of the right dispersion suppressor) is equal to the phase advance of one arc cell plus an integer.
- Although the insertions are not perfectly symmetric, we have preferred to keep some waist conditions at the middle. In other terms, we ask having $\alpha_x = \alpha_y = D'_x = 0$ at the middle of the insertion. We ask also to keep the chromatic derivative of α and the second-order dispersion derivative near 0: $A_x \approx A_y \approx dD'_x/d\delta \approx 0$.
- We match the Twiss parameters but also the Montague functions A_x, A_y, B_x, B_y and second-order dispersion $dD_x/d\delta$ and $dD'_x/d\delta$ at the entrance of the right arc.

2.2 FODO lattice

The collider arcs are based on quasi-FODO cells. However, the collider has to enable two optics with two different cell lengths: the so-called “long 90/90” and the simple “90/90 FODO” cells. Indeed, because of beam-beam effects, the collider needs to work with an enlarged momentum compaction for the Z/W operations. The direct consequence is two different patterns for the

quadrupole and sextupole families. That is why, in the 90/90 version, we can see the arc cell as a succession of 5 cells of about 52m each. The booster cell has to follow the same cell parameter as the collider to keep the same periodicity, which facilitates tunnel integration, installation, and connection to services. That is why the length of the booster arc cell is 260.554 m.

Moreover, to maximize the cancellation of the geometric aberrations introduced by the arc sextupoles, we require a phase advance of π in both planes between the sextupoles of a pair, which yields 4 constraints. We also adjust the global tune of the machine with a fine tuning of the arcs cells, which results in two additional constraints. The tune of the arc cell is then $1.25 \pm \epsilon_{x,y}$ with $\epsilon_{x,y} \ll 1$. That is why the arc cell requires 6 quadrupole families to tune the phase advances between the sextupole pairs and the global tune plus two sextupole families to tune the global chromaticity. The optical and chromatic functions in the arc cell based on a FODO lattice are shown in Fig. 6 (top).

In the CDR, the dispersion suppressors are made of 10 FODO cells. The quadrupoles of the dispersion suppressors are adjusted to cancel the dispersion and to match the optical functions at the arc entrance. The main reason of this configuration was to follow more precisely the FCC collider tunnel and to maximise the filling factor.

In the current version, the dispersion suppressor is made of 1.5 FODO arc cell and 2 FODO cells of the same type as the arcs with only one dipole per half-cell instead of 2 (see Fig. 6 (middle)). The length of the dipoles has been adjusted to minimize the second-order dispersion at the end of the dispersion suppressor. The dispersion naturally damps and we need to slightly tune the quadrupoles of the dispersion suppressor to cancel the dispersion, the second-order dispersion, and also to fix the phase advance to 180° between the last sextupole in the arcs and the dispersion suppressor entrance. The reason for this constraint is make possible a late insertion of an additional sextupole to cancel the geometric aberrations.

The dispersion suppressors and insertions have been matched according to the transparency conditions. The optical functions and second-order chromatic functions of one quarter of the booster based on a FODO lattice are shown in Fig. 6 (bottom).

2.3 Alternative: HFD lattice

The Hybrid FODO (HFD) lattice is an alternative to the FODO cell. The main motivation of this cell is to reduce the anharmonicity and second-order chromaticity of the FODO cell to enlarge the momentum acceptance and dynamic aperture. The main difference between the HFD and FODO cells are:

- The phase advances between the two sextupoles of the same pair are near π (and not exactly π).
- The dipoles do not have the same length, which enable a modulation of the distance between the quadrupoles. The total length of the dipoles stay the same, to keep the same curvature radius and thus radiated power per turn.
- The horizontal and vertical tunes are quite different. In the case of the FODO cell, we have about 1.25 in both planes against 1.25/1.15 for the HFD cell.

The optical functions and second-order chromatic functions in the arc cell and in one quarter of the booster based on a HFD lattice are respectively shown in Fig. 7 (top and bottom) .

2.4 Dynamic aperture and momentum acceptance

One of the main concerns is to get a sufficiently large dynamic aperture and momentum acceptance in order to keep the beam losses small at injection. The dynamic aperture without errors is calculated by scanning the initial particle positions that are stable on the x and y axes after 1000 turns, without taking into account synchrotron radiation damping. Different initial energy offsets between -2% and $+2\%$ are also considered to check the momentum acceptance. Figure 8 shows the resulting horizontal and vertical stable regions as a function of the energy offset, the dynamic aperture of the FODO and the Hybrid FODO lattice are compared. In both cases, we have enough margin to guarantee the stability of the injected beam. It is worth noticing that

Fig. 6: Optical functions (left) and second-order chromatic functions (right) in the arc cells (top), in the dispersion suppressor before section B (middle), or in the one quarter of the booster (bottom) with the version with FODO arc cells.

the transparency condition given by the periodicity of the Montague functions in the straight sections and the control of the second order dispersion, as described in section 2.1, greatly improve the dynamic aperture. Therefore, when more realistic optics for the insertions will be available, attention should be paid to ensure these periodicity conditions. The impact of the linear and non-linear imperfections on the stability region and a possible mitigation strategy are the next steps of investigation.

Fig. 7: Optical functions (left) and second-order chromatic functions (right) in the arc cells (top) and in one quarter of the booster (bottom) with the version with HFD arc cells.

Fig. 8: Horizontal (left) and vertical (right) Dynamic Aperture at injection as a function of momentum deviation for the FODO and the HFD optics. The normalized horizontal and vertical emittances used to compute the beam sizes are both 10 μm .

3 Injection and extraction

3.1 Injection system

The present baseline for the pre-injector complex ends with the high energy linac which provides trains of 4 electron or positron bunches separated by 25 ns and operating at 100 Hz. These trains

are accumulated in the booster up to a total of 1120 bunches (see Tab. 3). Each bunch is injected into its own bucket, and there is no bunch charge accumulation in the booster. Therefore, the injection scheme uses a fast kicker system capable of rising within 25 ns to allow for the accumulation of long trains.

The beam is produced at 20 GeV by the pre-injector complex and presents characteristics critical to the injection system concept. The bunch length and energy spread at injection listed in Tab. 3, are independent of the linac due to the presence of a bunch and energy compression system in the transfer line between the linac and the booster. However, bunch-to-bunch oscillations need to be accounted for, and discussions with linac experts concluded that the minimum expected transverse jitter at the output of the linac is around 1σ , requiring damping in the booster using an active injection damper. Longitudinal jitters, in both energy and time, should also be accounted for but remain to be studied further [4].

This section first discusses the design and hardware of the injection system, and then the concepts of the dump and extraction systems.

3.1.1 Injection concept

The pre-injector complex is located near the collider point A, with dedicated transfer lines joining the collider tunnel on each side of the straight section, as shown schematically in Fig. 4. The placement of the transfer lines was optimised to limit the radius of curvature, allowing reuse for hadrons up to several TeV (FCC-hh) and minimising the increase in lepton beam energy spread due to synchrotron radiation [5]. The resulting transfer lines reach the booster ring on both sides of the straight section, making injection within point A straight section of the booster impossible without dedicated sharp bending sections. The injected beam could follow the collider tunnel to the next straight section, but this would require almost 10 km of additional beamline to reach point L for the counterclockwise injection and point B for the clockwise injection. While it is usual to aim for injection in a dedicated straight section, several options for direct in-arc injection were explored [6].

The selected baseline injection scheme is implemented in the arc with the aim to minimise the required transfer line lengths as well as the changes required in the arc. Due to the strong synchrotron radiation emitted by the circulating beam inside the booster ring, in the horizontal plane, the selected injection scheme is applied in the vertical plane. Figure 9 shows the layout of counterclockwise injection in the 8th arc, between point A and point L of the collider (see Fig. 4). The scheme spans across two cells of the booster arc, each cell being 9 quadrupoles long. The second cell, from quadrupoles 218 to 228 contains the merging of the injection line with the booster ring and the injection septa. The first cell contains the kicker magnet, and both cells can be separated by an even number of cells, although placed contiguously in Fig. 9.

While the arc layout only has around 1 m of clearance between quadrupoles and dipoles, the first step is to free sufficient room to place the injection devices in the lattice. Taking advantage of the moderately low field of the dipoles, the present scheme replaces a few of the main dipoles with a variant of half the length but the same deflection and a larger vertical aperture to accommodate the injection trajectory. In the second cell, two dipoles are replaced symmetrically around quadrupole 222 to accommodate the septa without changing the reference trajectory outside that section. In the first cell, a single dipole is replaced, centred on the same longitudinal position as the one it replaces to once again preserve the reference trajectory. These modified dipoles are shown in cyan in Fig. 9 and their effect on the optics is very small, so that no re-matching is needed to replace them. However, the effect on the synchrotron radiation emitted through those dipoles has not been estimated, and its absorption downstream by both counterclockwise and clockwise beams may need to be considered.

The second requirement is an adapted injection optics with optimised beta function and phase advance. Increasing the beta function at the kicker and septa while preserving a phase advance close to 90° both contribute to increasing the effectiveness of the kicker deflection and increasing the distance between circulating and injected beams. The phase advance criterion is already satisfied by the nominal optics as it features an average phase advance of 90° (see Sec. 2.2). The

Fig. 9: Synoptic, optics, and vertical envelopes of the injection scheme for the beam circulating from right to left. The lower section shows the circulating and injected beam envelopes together with the aperture of the main arc elements.

optics is adjusted to increase the vertical beta function at the injection elements while preserving the Twiss parameters and phase advances at the cell's extremities and also minimising the changes to the horizontal optics. Figure 9 shows that the vertical beta function at both the kicker and septa regions reaches 300 m. It requires independent adjustment of the 6 families of the arc quadrupoles by up to approximately 20 %, but preserves the symmetry of the cell and its powering scheme. The effect of this dedicated optics on the chromatic functions was not computed, but it can be collapsed back to the nominal optics after the injection process is completed.

The placement of injection elements and the threading of the injected beam through the lattice elements is particularly challenging. We can see in the close-up of the septa region (Fig. 10) the injected beam overlapping with the top of the first modified dipole, but a custom channel could allow the passage of the injected beam. Following the injected trajectory, a channel will need to be established between the poles of the quadrupoles, but this seems to be realistic with the present quadrupole design in the grey part of the aperture, between 31.5 mm and 65 mm. Further downstream, the injected envelope passes approximately 1 mm from the edge of the first nominal dipole. However, detailed studies on the feasibility of the magnets and proposed channels for the injected beam will be needed.

The optimisation of the injection scheme was carried out using different definitions of the beam envelopes for the injected and circulating beams. For the circulating beam, the envelope is defined as $\pm 15\sigma$ with a normalized emittance of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ but without contribution from the momentum spread since the design vertical dispersion is null. However, the injected beam has a non-zero vertical dispersion in order to match the booster ring condition at the kicker, and this represents a large contribution to the beam size. We must also account for the jitter of the injected beam, of 1σ in the transverse space, with the energy jitter yet to be determined. The momentum spread of the injected beam may also evolve as the presently considered injected energy spread of 1×10^{-3} (see Tab. 3) uses an energy compression while the linac provides an energy spread of 2.5×10^{-3} . Therefore, the injected beam envelope uses a linear sum of $\pm 12\sigma$ of the betatron contribution and an energy spread of $\pm 5 \times 10^{-3}$. The momentum term is a major contribution to the beam size near the septa where the vertical dispersion is around 0.5 m.

The thin septum is the closest element to the circulating beam with its inside edge being at 2.8 mm from the envelope of the circulating beam as defined above. However, the injection scheme also assumes a vertical closed orbit bump of 8 mm at the thin septum to bring the circulating trajectory closer to the injected one. This bump could be made using the nominal closed orbit

Fig. 10: Close-up of the injection scheme near the septa region, using the same legend as Fig. 9.

correctors or dedicated magnets but was only modelled as a shift of the closed orbit in the present concept. Without the vertical bump, the thin septum is located 14.8 mm from the reference closed orbit. Inside the septum, the injected beam trajectory is placed closest to blade with an envelope of ± 4.4 mm to be compared with the septum aperture of 21 mm.

3.1.2 Injection hardware systems

The feasibility of the injection scheme relies upon the development and implementation of realistic hardware solutions largely based on existing technologies. This section discusses the present hardware concept of the injection scheme and some of the challenges.

Table 4: Injection septa main parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Thin Septum	Thick Septum
Max. physical length	[mm]		3000
Beam energy	[GeV]		20
Deflection angle	[mrad]		4.5
Equivalent magnetic length	[mm]	2000	2000
Apparent septum thickness	[mm]	10	18
Gap width (\perp to deflection)	[mm]	15	15
Gap height (in plane of deflection)	[mm]	21	19
Operating mode			DC

The main requirements and the selected baseline solution for the septa systems are summarised in Tab. 4. Due to the limited bandwidth a septum can achieve, the baseline proposal foresees under-vacuum DC magnetic septa. With the small beam sizes and apertures, it may be of interest to be able to adjust the septum position with respect to the circulating beam. A manual adjustment mechanism could be implemented for occasional alignment after survey or beam measurement, but a remote positioning system is not part of the baseline.

Other septa technologies are considered for the injection system but the challenges they presented excluded them from this baseline. A pulsed eddy current septum design eliminates the need for separate thin and thick septa, leveraging existing technology while incorporating water cooling to manage the high current density resulting from the rapid 100 Hz repetition rate. However, investigations are required for aspects such as blade positioning, power feedthrough, insulation,

and beam impedance shielding. A permanent magnet solution could reduce the power consumption but several aspects such as the dimensions, vacuum behaviour, and ageing in the presence of high radiation require further development to validate it.

Table 5: Injection kicker requirements where values with “~” are still under discussion.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Deflection	[mrad]	0.09
Rise time	[ns]	<25
Fall time	[ns]	~<50
Flat-top length	[ns]	75
Flat-top stability	[%]	~ ± 1
Maximum repetition rate	[Hz]	100
Effective length	[m]	1

For the injection kicker, a stripline design has been selected to comply with the required fast rise time of 25 ns and its main parameters are listed in Tab. 5 [7]. The short flat-top length of 75 ns allows for the use of a new inductive adder technology [8]. Two generators will produce opposite polarity pulses feeding the two stripline electrodes.

A fast rise time is required to accumulate long trains into the booster ring but imposes strong constraints on the maximum cable length between the generators (see Tab. 8), which are placed in a well shielded location, and the kicker. If these requirements cannot be fulfilled in the arc, the injection scheme could be slightly modified by moving the kicker part to the closest straight section and allowing the beam to undergo betatron oscillations over the few kilometres separating the septa and the kicker.

To mitigate the effects of cable length on the quality of the deflecting pulse, it is necessary to design appropriate pulse modulation and additional filtering elements. High levels of radiation, mostly produced by the circulating collider beam’s synchrotron radiation, may impact the lifetime of equipment, particularly high voltage cables. Beam impedance, both regarding the effect of the injection elements on the dynamics of the circulating beam and the effect of the RF heating on the injection devices themselves, requires comprehensive modelling, including a proper design of the stripline terminating resistor network. Therefore, the present solution could be developed towards a technical design but could also benefit from further R&D to apply newer technologies.

Table 6: Injection kicker system main parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Kicker/system		1/2
Technology		Stripline
Impedance	[Ω]	50
Current	[kA]	0.3
Voltage	[kV]	±16
Element aperture	[mm]	30
Integrated magnetic field	[mT m]	34
Integrated electric field	[MV]	0.9
Effective length	[m]	1
Physical length	[m]	1.4

3.2 Extraction and dump systems

The point B technical straight section houses the booster-to-collider transfer as well as the booster and collider dump systems (see Fig. 4). The extraction system is used to transport the beam from

the booster towards the collider and is independent of the dump system, which can safely extract and discard the beam at any time.

The beam accumulated and accelerated in the booster may be spread over the entire circumference with up to 1120 bunches for the Z-mode and up to 182.5 GeV for the $t\bar{t}$ -mode (see Tab. 3). This requires that the dump system be capable of a pulse at least the duration of one full revolution, 304 μs . The extraction system could potentially use shorter pulsing by extracting only part of the circulating beam on the condition that it would rise and fall within the time between trains, presently 1.1 μs to 1.5 μs . These requirements mostly concern the kicker system and are listed in Tab. 7.

Following an overview of the extraction and dump system layouts within the straight section of point B, this section will discuss critical aspects of machine protection. Subsequently, we will discuss the specific hardware choices for these systems and the associated technical challenges.

3.2.1 Layout and optics

The technical straight sections of the booster all feature an achromatic FODO lattice with only two quadrupole families and a strong beating over a period of four quadrupoles. This optics maintains a phase advance of approximately 90° between focusing quadrupoles and provides larger beta functions than in the arc. Figure 11 shows the optics and layout along the whole straight section, including the matching sections to the arc on both sides.

Fig. 11: Synoptic, optics, and vertical envelopes of the injection scheme for the beam circulating from right to left. The lower section shows the circulating and injected beam envelopes together with the aperture of the main arc elements.

The baseline design is fully symmetric for clockwise and counterclockwise beams, with the extraction systems placed at the center of the straight section and the dump systems located at the entrance of the straight section for each incoming beam. The dump system placement allows the dumped beam almost 1 km of free space before reaching the other side of the straight section where the dumps will be located. It also follows the presently proposed collider dump system placement and could potentially use the same dump as well. The extraction system is located in the center of the straight section and extracts towards the second half where the collider injection is located.

The nominal optics with large beta function and near 90° phase advance already match the typical requirements of an extraction system. The layout of the straight section features long spaces drift spaces between quadrupoles of approximately 50 m, allowing sufficient space to comfortably

install all the extraction systems. Therefore, both the nominal optics and quadrupole layout are preserved for the baseline concept, although further optimisation could be considered once the design evolves towards technical implementation.

Fig. 12: Close-up view of synoptic, layout and apertures for the clockwise extraction (a) and dump region (b).

The extraction system is located at the precise center of the straight section and uses two groups of kickers on either side of quadrupole $mqd1.s2.022$ to enable the use of the same magnets for extracting both clockwise and counterclockwise beams (see Fig. 12a). Although we presently consider two independent kicker systems for hardware specifications and costing, this symmetry could be exploited at a later stage to reduce cost or provide redundancy in the system. The extraction kicker requirements are listed in Tab. 7, and the kicker angle of 0.43 mrad allows reaching a large offset at the downstream septa. Due to the symmetry of the extraction trajectories towards the sides of the straight sections, each beam has its own septum, which creates a deflection of 2 mrad each.

Table 7: Dump and extraction kickers requirements where values with “~” are still under discussion.

Parameter	Unit	Extraction	Dump
Total deflection	[mrad]	0.43	0.3
Rise time	[μ s]	$\lesssim 1.1$	$\lesssim 1.5$
Fall time	[μ s]	$\gtrsim 1.5$	Any
Flat-top length	[μ s]	30-150 (pulsed) or 304	304
Flat-top stability	[%]	$\sim \pm 0.5$	$\sim \pm 5.0$
Repetition rate	[Hz]	10 (pulsed) or 0.3	1
Available length	[m]	~ 50	~ 50

The dump system is very similar, although one entirely dedicated system is placed at each entrance of the straight section (see Fig. 12b). In this case, the kickers deflect the circulating beam by 0.3 mrad and the downstream septa by a total of 4.8 mrad.

The envelopes in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 use the largest possible geometrical emittance and momentum spread, which are reached for the tt-mode (see Tab. 3). For the circulating beam,

the envelope uses $\pm 15\sigma$ of that largest possible beam, while the extracted and dumped envelopes use $\pm 10\sigma$. The apertures and strengths used in this baseline concept are capable of transporting those envelopes, but a more detailed study, including kicker technology choices and filling scheme requirements, will be needed to finalise the requirements (see Tab. 7) and converge on the technology choices.

3.2.2 Machine protection considerations

The following considerations refer to the Z-mode operation which is the most critical from the machine protection point of view.

The booster is filled with bunches of up to 2.5×10^{10} particles per bunch. After being accelerated to 45.6 GeV the bunches are extracted into the transfer lines towards the collider by means of fast pulsed kickers. The same kind of magnets are used to extract the beam towards the external dump line as a consequence of an operator request or an emergency. In this case the beam can be extracted at any energy between 20 GeV and 50 GeV (energy overshoot).

The extraction magnets, being operated at high voltage, are prone to spurious firing, which can result in mis-kicking the circulating beam that can then be lost in the booster ring or in the transfer lines. Absorbers must be installed at dedicated locations in the booster ring and the transfer line towards the collider to protect the machine aperture against these losses. One of the challenges for the FCC-ee is to safely handle the high stored energy (up to 17.5 MJ in the collider) and, due to the extremely small transverse beam size, the energy density (up to 4.6 GJ mm^{-2} assuming a normalised emittance of $2 \mu\text{m}$ and a β of 100 m) of the operational beams. In order to limit the criticality of the beam extraction and transfer and to allow designing protection elements capable of withstanding a full beam impact, it has been decided to limit the number of bunches in the booster to 1120 for Z-mode (0.175 MJ stored energy). Despite the reduced intensity, such beams remain extremely critical and potentially destructive. Additional measures must be considered to ensure the safety and integrity of all the machine components, possibly including the protection absorbers, in case of a failure during the extraction and transfer processes. The optics at the location of the protection element should be designed with the aim of maximising the beam transverse size to minimise the energy density and reduce the stresses on the absorber materials. The possibility of further increasing the number of kickers to reduce the voltage (e.g. the risk of erratic firing) and the consequences of a magnet failure is taken into account, as well as the option of transferring the 1120 circulating bunches to the collider in chunks and not all at once. The latter option would also allow to reduce the flat-top length of the kicker waveform, which could help achieve the required constraint of pulse flatness within $\pm 0.5\%$, but would impact the filling of the collider and has to be carefully evaluated.

The position of the beam in the extraction and dump regions must be monitored and interlocked to avoid drifts beyond well-defined limits. If the orbit crosses the limits, the beam has to be aborted to the dump. The extraction kickers must pulse only at top energy, while dump kickers strength has to be scaled with the beam energy. A dedicated system that tracks the energy, inhibits the extraction kickers from pulsing until flat-top, and verifies that the dump kickers voltage correctly follows the energy ramp has to be implemented. Ideally, the number of dump kickers should be such as to allow a loss-free extraction at all energies and when within the position limits, even with one missing kicker. An important aspect to evaluate is the required reaction time to detect anomalies and safely dispose the beam.

3.2.3 Extraction hardware systems

For the booster extraction, a ferrite loaded lumped inductance magnet is the preferred choice due to its simple and robust design. A Marx generator can be used to drive the magnet. Design considerations must focus on achieving the long flat top while providing the required field homogeneity. The required total capacitance of the Marx generator to meet both needs is significant, potentially requiring substantial storage space. Additionally, solutions to limit the pulse droop shall be properly designed. Keeping the beam coupling impedance low is crucial to ensure both magnet integrity and to limit its impact on beam quality and operation; for this reason beam screen

Table 8: Extraction and Dump Kicker System Main Parameters

Parameter	Unit	Extraction	Dump
Kicker/system		10/2	6/2
Technology		Ferrite Lumped Inductance	
Impedance	[Ω]	10	2.5
Current	[kA]	1.4	1.7
Voltage	[kV]	14.5	5
Element aperture	[mm]	70	70
Integrated field	[mT m]	26	30
Effective length	[m]	1	1
Physical length	[m]	1.4	1.4

solutions need to be studied. In addition, the radiation environment is a major concern, requiring special attention to the location of connection boxes and cable routing. The main parameters of the booster extraction system are summarised in Tab. 8.

The septa used for extraction towards the collider will only function at one energy, which is different for each mode. In operation, these septa will reach their nominal field for a short time only during extraction. Therefore, the selected baseline is a pulsed system outside vacuum, which provides the required blade thickness and aperture (see Tab. 9). This system will be fixed, and no remote or manual adjustment of the blade position is considered. A permanent magnet solution was considered, but the present estimates do not allow reaching the required blade thickness for the current concept.

Table 9: Extraction and dump septa main parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Extraction Septa	Dump Septa
Max. available length	[mm]		20
Max. beam energy	[GeV]		182.5
Deflection angle	[mrad]	2	3×1.6
Equivalent magnetic length	[mm]	1500	3×1500
Apparent septum thickness	[mm]	10	25
Gap height (\perp to deflection)	[mm]	14	20
Gap width (in plane of deflection)	[mm]	20	23
Operating mode		Pulsed	Slow ramped DC

3.2.4 Dump hardware systems

Similarly, for the dump system, a ferrite-loaded lumped inductance magnet is considered the optimal choice. In addition, using the same magnet design for booster extraction is expected to benefit from cost reductions through design standardisation. An LHC beam dump system type generator is chosen to drive the magnet due to its proven reliability [9]. This is based on a main capacitor discharge stage followed by one or more droop compensation stages to achieve the long flat-top. The generator must be designed to be able to discharge and recharge to follow the energy overshoot scheme. Critical factors that will need to be accounted for in the final design optimisation include the beam coupling impedance, heat load, and the radiation environment. The main parameters of the booster dump kicker system are summarised in Tab. 8.

The dump septa also follow the energy of the circulating beam to safely channel the dumped beam at any moment of the cycle. Several accumulation and ramping scenarios of the booster were considered, including the energy overshoot at the Z-mode. For this, the proposed topology is a slowly ramped DC septum outside vacuum with a fixed blade and no position adjustment possible. The significant maximum power dissipation of more than 22 kW per unit requires water-cooling and accordingly, a larger apparent blade thickness of 25 mm (see Tab. 4).

4 Collective effects

4.1 Baseline assumptions for collective effects studies

The high-energy booster may experience impedance-induced instabilities that depend on various parameters and can manifest as short-range or long-range effects. Some parameters, such as the number of bunches and the number of particles per bunch, depend on the cycling and operation mode. Other parameters, such as the momentum compaction factor, depend on the optics design. Impedance contributions also play a significant role. At this stage of the study, only resistive wall contributions have been considered. Although resistive wall effects do not encompass all impedance contributions, they dominate and are crucial for defining physical parameters of the beam-pipe, such as its diameter and material, which in turn affect the vacuum system and magnet designs, among other important subsystems.

4.2 Mismatched beams at injection

The high-energy booster stands between the high-energy LINAC and the main ring. Its ability to deliver a beam with the appropriate requirements depends on several parameters, including those of the injected beam from the high-energy LINAC. While the booster design proves robust to various transverse parameters of the beam at injection energy, the longitudinal parameters can cause significant mismatch and microwave instabilities. Therefore, a study has been performed to confirm that, apart from the energy acceptance, the injected beam does not trigger instabilities. The injector complex has the ability to provide beams with specific bunch lengths and energy dispersion. A two-dimensional parametric scan has been performed at injection energy. The longitudinal mismatch ξ_z has been quantified in terms of:

$$\xi_z = \frac{\sigma_z^{\text{eq}}}{\sigma_z^{\text{inj}}} \quad (1)$$

where σ_z^{inj} is the bunch length at injection and σ_z^{eq} is the bunch length at equilibrium. Fig. 13 shows that the baseline bunch lengths and energy dispersion requirements from the LINAC provide a significant safety margin regarding longitudinal mismatch and microwave instabilities. Fig. 13 also rules out a configuration where an energy compressor would not be used after the high-energy LINAC, resulting in an injection energy dispersion of 0.25% and a bunch length of 1 mm. The figure shows that the present baseline injection parameters from the high-energy LINAC, with $\sigma_z = 4$ mm and $\sigma_e = 0.1\%$, allow for a significant margin to avoid mismatch and microwave instabilities at injection energy.

Another effect being studied is the result of a transverse jitter of up to 1σ in the vertical and horizontal planes. Present particle tracking studies do not show any effect at equilibrium. However, amplitude detuning has not yet been taken into account, and these results need to be confirmed with more realistic simulation parameters.

4.3 Coupled bunch instabilities

4.3.1 Transverse coupled bunch instabilities due to resistive wall impedance

Transverse resistive wall wakefields act as a long-range effect. They can lead to transverse coupled-bunch instabilities that are destructive to the beam. Given the following assumptions, one can estimate analytically the transverse growth rate due to coupled bunches: 1. Equally spaced Gaussian bunches 2. Only coherent bunch modes 3. Only the most prominent radial mode in the longitudinal azimuthal mode.

With these assumptions, the transverse growth rate τ_{\perp} [10] can be expressed by:

$$\tau_{\perp} \sim \frac{N_p \cdot N_b}{4\pi \cdot Q_{x,y} \cdot E} \cdot \Re(Z_{\perp}) \cdot \mathcal{G}(Q_{x,y}, \sigma_z, \sigma_e) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 13: Kernel density estimate of the longitudinal mismatch as a function of bunch length and energy dispersion at injection. The energy considered is 20 GeV and the different booster parameters considered are those of the Z-pole operation (see Tab. 3). The target circle shows the present baseline injection parameters to the high-energy booster.

where N_p is the number of particles per bunch, N_b is the number of bunches, $Q_{x,y}$ is the transverse tune, E is the energy, Z_{\perp} is the transverse impedance, and \mathcal{G} a factor which can be approximated to 1 in our case. With the Z operation mode being the worst-case scenario, one can estimate the growth rate as a function of the mode numbers. By normalizing the modes, one can compare the growth rate for two different booster configurations, namely PA31.0 (2023 design) and PA31.3 (2024 design). Fig. 14(b) shows that the growth rate has been reduced in the new baseline design compared to the previous one. The most drastic change is at the Z-pole operation, which represents the worst-case scenario. For this case, we observe a reduction from 374 s^{-1} (i.e., 8.7 turns) in the 2023 design to 10 s^{-1} (i.e., 310 turns) in the 2024 design. This is due to several important changes including: the increase of the beam pipe diameter from 50 mm to 60 mm and the reduction of the number of bunches from 15 880 to 1120 bunches. While the new growth rates are still faster than the transverse synchrotron damping ($\sim 30\,000$ turns), they reduce the constraints on the dampers needed to mitigate such coupled-bunch instabilities.

Fig. 14: Left: Cavities HOM induced coupled bunch instabilities (CBI) threshold currents in the transverse (pink) and longitudinal (blue) planes, with (lines) and without (bars) a feedback system, and for the CDR design (plain) and an alternative design (dashed/hashed). Right: Resistive wall transverse impedance induced transverse growth rates as a function of the mode number for the PA31.3 2024 baseline (hashed-red) and the PA31.0 2023 baseline (plain-blue).

4.3.2 Coupled bunch instabilities due to cavities high order modes

The beam is injected into the booster from the high-energy LINAC at 20 GeV. Due to the rapid energy ramp-up and extraction compared to the accumulation time, the injection energy dominates during booster operation. This decreases the shunt impedance threshold, potentially triggering coupled bunch instabilities driven by the high-order modes of RF cavities. Considering the maximum shunt impedance that the radiation damping is able to counteract, one can express instability thresholds in terms of a normalized beam current I_{norm} defined as:

$$I_{norm} = \frac{I_{nom}}{I_b},$$

where I_b is the threshold mean beam current, and I_{nom} is the nominal mean beam current. Using the parameters in Table 10, and comparing two different cavity designs, Figure 14(a) shows that the threshold due to transverse instabilities is exceeded in all cases. Therefore, a transverse damping system is required in all operational modes. The same figure shows that a longitudinal damping system is not necessary for the Z , W , and ZH operation modes.

Table 10: Parameters used for cavities HOM induced CBI, with FB indicating the feedback system and SR indicating synchrotron radiation damping.

Mode	Unit	Z	W	Higgs	ttbar
Energy	[GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Synchrotron tune Q_s		0.0262	0.0262	0.0262	0.0262
Transverse betatron tune β_{\perp}		61	61	61	61
Current I_b	[mA]	14.83	11.79	2.01	0.297
Slip factor η	$[10^{-6}]$	7.12	7.12	7.12	7.12
Number of cavities		8	28	108	488
τ_{\parallel}^{SR}	[ms]	4150	4238	4180	4205
τ_{\parallel}^{FB}	[ms]	23	23	22	22
τ_{\perp}^{SR}	[ms]	8301	8477	8361	8409
τ_{\perp}^{FB}	[ms]	30	30	30	30

To further investigate and compare cavity impedances for the two studied designs, it is crucial to assess if any resonance modes exceed the threshold shunt impedances in the transverse (Z_{\perp}) or longitudinal (Z_{\parallel}) planes. These shunt impedances can be expressed as functions of critical parameters:

$$Z_{\parallel}(f) = \frac{2E \cdot Q_s}{f \cdot e \cdot I_b \cdot \eta \cdot \tau_{\parallel}} \quad \text{and} \quad Z_{\perp} = \frac{2E \cdot T_0}{e \cdot I_b \cdot \beta_{\perp} \cdot \tau_{\perp}},$$

where f is the frequency, E is the beam energy, Q_s is the synchrotron tune, e is the charge of particles, I_b is the mean beam current, η is the slippage factor, T_0 is the revolution period, β_{\perp} is the transverse betatron tune, and τ represents the damping time. This investigation assumes a worst-case scenario where the operation mode is the Z -pole, due to its highest bunch population and number of bunches. With this assumption, Figure 15 illustrates that in the longitudinal plane, the proposed alternative design outperforms the CDR baseline by approximately a factor of 4, effectively damping the resonant mode around 2.4 GHz without necessitating a bunch-by-bunch system. Conversely, for the transverse plane, both designs perform similarly. In this case, both designs exceed the SR damping threshold and demonstrate the need for a feedback system.

4.4 Single Bunch instabilities

Single bunch instabilities that may arise in the high-energy booster and hinder achieving technical targets are of two types: microwave instabilities (MI) and transverse mode coupling instabilities (TMCI) (see [10]). The bunch population thresholds for these instabilities can be expressed as:

Fig. 15: Longitudinal (left panel) and transverse plane (right panel) impedances (black and grey curves) against thresholds computed from Equation (4.3.2), with FB indicating the feedback system and SR indicating synchrotron radiation damping for the Z-pole operation.

$$N_{p,th}^{TMCI} = \frac{Q_{x,y} \cdot Q_s \cdot E \cdot \sigma_z}{\Im Z_{\perp} \cdot e \cdot c}, \quad N_{p,th}^{MI} \propto \frac{n \cdot \alpha_c \cdot E \cdot \sigma_e \cdot \sigma_z}{|Z_{\parallel}|}, \quad (3)$$

where $Q_{x,y}$ is the transverse tune, Q_s is the synchrotron tune, E is the energy, σ_z is the bunch length, Z_{\perp} is the transverse impedance, α_c is the momentum compaction factor, and Z_{\parallel} is the longitudinal impedance.

Although these two effects are interconnected, transverse mode coupling instabilities are particularly critical due to their potential for destructive transverse exponential growth in the beam. In contrast, microwave instabilities typically lead to longitudinal emittance growth, which, under the injected beam parameters, remains within the constraints defined for extraction to the main ring.

Designing the high-energy booster requires balancing multiple dominant effects outlined in Equation (3). Among these, resistive wall contributions dominate the impedance effects, while the momentum compaction factor significantly influences the optimal choice of optical design.

The following analyzes the influence of these parameters on transverse mode coupling instabilities.

4.4.1 Resistive wall contribution

The circumference of the booster ring closely resembles that of the main ring, making the resistive wall (RW) impedance the primary contributor to collective effects in both rings. In our investigation, we utilized the VACI Suite [11] to examine different materials and radii, with the results being directly employed in XSuite [12] and PyHEADTAIL[13] for beam dynamics simulations. These tools allowed us to precisely model the behavior of the beam and the interaction with the surrounding environment, ensuring accurate predictions and optimizations for the beam pipe design. In our detailed study of beam pipe materials, we explored three scenarios: a copper beam pipe (Cu), a stainless steel pipe (SS), and a stainless steel pipe with an internal copper coating (SS-Cu). We examined various thicknesses of the copper coating and ultimately selected a 1 mm copper layer as the optimal configuration. The different scenarios (Cu, SS, and SS-Cu) are illustrated in Figure 16. The choice of materials was critical in managing the RW impedance and thereby influencing the overall beam stability and performance.

Fig. 16: (a) Longitudinal impedance and (b) Dipolar impedance for a pipe with $R=30$ mm and $L=1$ m, for three different scenarios (Cu, SS, and SS-Cu).

Given that the geometry of the beam pipe is round, we did not encounter any detuning (quadrupolar) impedance, even with the coated pipe that featured a narrow strip of copper missing inside. This absence of a continuous copper layer might have been expected to induce detuning impedance, but VACI results indicated that the presence of this strip had negligible effects. Therefore, our final design incorporates the SS-Cu configuration with a 1 mm copper coating, balancing material properties and impedance requirements for optimal performance.

4.4.2 Beam-pipe Radius and Material

As highlighted in Sec. 4.4.1, two materials were considered for the beam vacuum chamber: stainless steel and copper. Stainless steel offers advantages such as lower initial cost and reduced eddy currents induced by magnetic field ramps during acceleration. However, it comes with increased longitudinal and transverse impedance (see Fig.16). Given the low magnetic fields involved, eddy currents are not a concern, allowing for a 1 mm copper coating: beyond approximately 2 kHz, the skin depth ensures the beam interacts predominantly with the copper layer.

The impact on beam dynamics was assessed using the PyHEADTAIL¹ tracking code [13].

A comparison was conducted on a circular beam pipe made of either copper or stainless steel, each with a diameter of 50 mm, using the PA31.0 baseline design (2023 CDR baseline) for the Z-pole operation. A significant increase in bunch length and thus longitudinal emittance was observed with a stainless steel vacuum chamber maintaining a 50 mm diameter. This necessitates an increase in the inner diameter of the stainless steel beam pipe. Consequently, an investigation into the optimal beam pipe diameter for stainless steel was conducted. Modal analysis following methods outlined in [14] indicated that a minimum beam-pipe diameter threshold of 70 mm could be set, with considerations allowing a diameter up to 100 mm when accounting for impedance margins.

4.4.3 Momentum Compaction Variation

For a given bunch of particles, variations in the relative path length due to changes in momentum can significantly affect TMCI bunch population thresholds, potentially triggering or mitigating coupled mode instabilities. This is quantified by the momentum compaction variation. A methodology similar to that in Sec. 4.4.2 was employed to study the momentum compaction-related thresholds and guide optics design choices. Fig.17 (a) illustrates that the PA31.0 design following the CDR 2023 baseline for $t\bar{t}$ operation ($\alpha_c = 7.34 \times 10^{-6}$) with a 50 mm diameter copper beam pipe resides in an unstable region. In contrast, the Z-pole operation ($\alpha_c = 1.49 \times 10^{-5}$), with

¹<https://github.com/PyCOMPLETE/PyHEADTAIL>

Fig. 17: Real part of the tune shift of the first azimuthal transverse coherent oscillation modes normalized by the synchrotron tune as a function of the momentum compaction factor (left) and the beam-pipe diameter (right) for the Z-operation mode. For (a), a copper beam-pipe of 50 mm diameter and a bunch population of 2.5×10^{10} particles are considered. For (b), a stainless steel beam-pipe of 50 mm diameter with a bunch population of 2.5×10^{10} particles and a momentum compaction $\alpha_c = 7.34 \times 10^{-6}$ are considered.

nearly double the momentum compaction, falls within a stable zone. Notably, the momentum compaction at the Z-pole closely approaches the stability threshold, suggesting an adjustment rather than doubling is sufficient for stable operation.

4.4.4 Bunch Population Variation

As discussed in Sec. 4.4.2 and 4.4.3, a high-energy booster design featuring a 50 mm diameter beam pipe, whether made of copper or stainless steel, coupled with an optics design having a momentum compaction of $\alpha_c = 7.34 \times 10^{-6}$, proves impractical. Conversely, adopting a single optics design instead of separate values for different operation modes offers benefits. A compromise was reached, maintaining a single momentum compaction value ($\alpha_c = 7.12 \times 10^{-6}$) while increasing the beam pipe diameter from 50 mm to 60 mm and opting for copper as the beam pipe material. Fig. 18 demonstrates that this new baseline design increases the TMCI threshold bunch population from 2.5×10^{10} to 5.7×10^{10} . Additionally, the incorporation of a 300-turn transverse damper (see Sec. 4.3) further enhances the threshold and safety margins. These results, however, require validation with a more comprehensive machine impedance model.

It is essential to note that these findings provide preliminary evaluations of collective effects on booster beam dynamics at low energy and high bunch population. Self-consistent simulations, incorporating intra-beam scattering, wakefields, and synchrotron radiation effects, are necessary for a thorough assessment of their impact on longitudinal and transverse motion during accumulation, ramp-up, and flat-top stages (see Sec. 9).

5 Magnet systems

5.1 General parameters

The requirements for the arc magnets are based on the FODO lattice described in section 2.2 and summarized in Table 11. In this version, all arc dipoles are the same. The dipoles in the dispersion suppressors are slightly longer and require different field levels but will have a common cross section with the arc dipoles. Currently, the FODO arc cell uses 6 quadrupole circuits leading to similar integrated gradients for all quadrupoles. Therefore, one quadrupole design is used throughout the lattice. In the case of the sextupoles, the dispersion is twice smaller in the defocusing sextupoles than in the focusing sextupoles. Therefore the defocusing sextupoles require twice the integrated gradient. This has been achieved by using a common cross section for both sextupoles and making

Fig. 18: Real part of the tune shift of the first azimuthal transverse coherent oscillation modes normalized by the synchrotron tune as a function of bunch population for the PA31.0 2023 CDR baseline (left) and the PA31.3 2024 baseline design (right).

the de-focusing sextupoles twice as long. The specifications for the correctors come from the section 8. The interconnection distance between two dipoles is 400 mm. The distance between the quadrupoles or sextupoles and the other correctors is 150 mm. Nevertheless, the distance between the dipoles and the first element near the quadrupoles is a 780 mm, leaving some margin to optimise the inter element distances. In the following sections, we will describe the technical solutions and performances for the main magnets of the arcs: the dipoles, quadrupoles, and sextupoles.

Table 11: Magnet requirements for the FODO lattice V24.

	Dipole	Quadrupole	Sextupole		Corrector
			Focus	Defocus	
Total number in lattice...	6176	3344	576	560	3344
... of which in arcs	5536	2768	576	560	2768
Aperture [mm]			65		
Length [m]	11	1.3	0.7	1.4	< 0.3
Max strength [†] , arc (extraction, $t\bar{t}$)	58.9 mT	28.7 T m ⁻¹	1141 T m ⁻²	1210 T m ⁻²	20 mT m
Min strength [†] , arc (injection, 20 GeV)	6.5 mT	3.2 T m ⁻¹	126 T m ⁻²	134 T m ⁻²	

[†] Sextupole strength given as B'' , $B'' = 2S$

5.2 Dipoles

The general parameters of the proposed dipole are summarized in Table 12. The field range for the dipole is 6.5 mT to 58.9 mT. The outer transverse dimensions of the dipole are 206 mm × 125 mm. The field map in the yoke at $t\bar{t}$ extraction is shown in Fig. 19.

The hysteretic effects were numerically simulated on a linear up and down ramp from the injection energy to the $t\bar{t}$ energy (corresponding to a linear ramp from 6.5 mT to 58.9 mT, see Fig. 20). The field quality in the good field region has been evaluated at different times of the ramp including the hysteretic effects with $H_c = 26$ A/m: at the beginning of the ramp (point A), at the middle of up-ramp (point B), at the top (point C), at the middle of the down-ramp (point D), and at the end of the cycle (point E). The worst case is at the beginning of the ramp. The harmonic component b_3 stays below a few units, which is acceptable for the beam dynamics.

In addition to numerical simulation, a magnet from CERN stock with similar dimensions and materials to the proposed dipoles has been measured. The parameters of the proposed dipole and the dipole we measured are compared in Table 13. The aims were 1) validate the simulation tools and 2) give an indication of the feasible field quality across the booster cycle. The simulations

Table 12: General parameters of the arc dipole magnets.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Strength, B , 20 GeV to 182.5 GeV	mT	6.5 - 58.9
Aperture (horizontal \times vertical)	mm ²	130 \times 65
Magnetic length	m	11
Outer envelope	mm ²	206 \times 125
Peak current	A_{pk}	3065
RMS current, $t\bar{t}$	A_{RMS}	1760
Magnet resistance	m Ω	0.70
Magnet inductance	μ H	44
Peak voltage, magnet	V	2.2
Peak voltage, octant (ex. cables)	V	1537
Conductor (Aluminium)	mm ²	12 \times 79, \varnothing 7
Turns		1
Current density, $t\bar{t}$	A/mm ²	1.92
Active mass (bus bars and yoke)	kg	1225

Fig. 19: Field map in the yoke of the baseline dipole magnet at $t\bar{t}$ energy. The calculations were performed with ANSYS Maxwell.

matched well with the measurement results. The simulations predicted the transfer function within 1%, and the harmonics within ± 0.15 units across the full cycle, giving confidence in the numerical simulation method. Throughout the full $t\bar{t}$ cycle, the measured harmonic field error was below 1×10^{-4} with a reference radius $R_{ref} = 10$ mm, giving confidence that acceptable field quality is feasible despite the low field, 6.5 mT, at injection. Due to the lower ratio of flux path to gap in the booster dipole, we can expect a lower hysteretic effect in the booster dipoles than the measured magnet.

Fig. 20: Left: Considered current cycle for $t\bar{t}$ operation. Right: Field quality in the good field region at different times of the current cycle.

Table 13: Comparison of the booster dipole and the measured magnet.

	Booster dipole	Magnet measured
Approximate mean flux length [mm]	270	460
Aperture [mm ²]	65 × 130	63 × 131
Gap to flux path length	1:4	1:7
Steel	M270-50A	M270-50A

The next step to validate the booster dipole design is to produce and test a short prototype. The number of turns is increased in the short prototype magnet for convenience; however, the short prototype magnet remains a valid representation of the baseline dipole. The length of the model magnet is determined as 500 mm.

5.3 Quadrupoles and sextupoles

The quadrupoles and sextupoles have been designed with relatively high gradients. The motivation is to minimise the length of the short straight sections, thereby increasing the dipole filling factor and reducing the synchrotron radiation losses. This objective is concordant with minimising the lifetime costs, as it increases the utilisation of the materials and reduces the coil length. However, there is an optimum beyond which saturation and high current density make the design too inefficient to justify the material saved.

A parametric code was developed to generate the cross sections of the quadrupoles and sextupoles and numerically simulate them. This code has been used to optimise the designs, both stand alone and in a global sense considering the impacts on other systems for example the powering. The stand alone optimisation was performed solving the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) at each step. However, when integrated with the global optimisation the solution time became prohibitive. Therefore, the parametric code was used to create design space maps, which could then be quickly interpolated during the global optimisation. The maps plotted stored magnetic energy, magnetic efficiency and yoke cross section as a function of current density and pole width. Pole width trades magnetic efficiency with iron utilisation and current density trades electrical efficiency with copper utilisation. From the three interpolated variables and the number of turns a design can be specified: the required Ampere-turns from efficiency and bulk current density; the cooling hole diameter is solved for a given temperature rise and pressure using Newton-Raphson; the resistance from cooling hole diameter and filling factor; the inductance from magnetic energy and turns; and the mass from yoke cross-section and the coil.

The parameters of the proposed quadrupole and sextupole magnets are summarised in Table 14. The field maps for the quadrupole and sextupole magnets at $t\bar{t}$ energy are given in Fig. 21.

In conclusion, the headline magnet requirements of v24 FODO optics are technically feasible including low dipole field and lens strengths. There is a large design space of feasible magnets, giving an opportunity for holistic design and a cost optimised solution. Open questions for the design optimisation to include: increasing the yoke thickness of the dipole to provide additional radiation shielding, see Fig. 41; increasing the operation temperature of the magnets to improve the efficiency of waste heat recovery, industrialisation and design for manufacture and assembly, and detailed integration with the other technical systems.

6 Structural supporting system

The current FCC-ee layout has a circumference of around 90 km, and about 85% i.e. 77 km are taken by the arcs. These arcs are made of half cells, about 3000 in all, and consist of a Short Straight Section (SSS) with quadrupole, sextupoles, beam diagnostics and correction, followed by a long dipole length that can be achieved with a series of 2 or 3 interconnected magnets. This chapter describes the optimisation of booster supporting structures to maximise its performance,

Table 14: General parameters for the quadrupole and sextupole magnets.

Parameter	Unit	Quadrupole	Sextupole	
			Defocus	Focus
Strength, B'	T m^{-1}	30	–	–
Strength, B''	T m^{-2}	–	1210	1140
Aperture diameter	mm		65	
Length	m	1.3	1.4	0.7
Outer envelope	mm	$\varnothing 584$	$\varnothing 305$	
Peak current	A_{pk}	1937	561	525
RMS current, $t\bar{t}$	A_{RMS}	1113	322	302
Magnet resistance	$\text{m}\Omega$	2.9	52	27
Magnet inductance	mH	3.6	8.8	4.4
Peak voltage magnet	V	27	51	24
Peak voltage, half-octant	kV	0.92	1.7	0.80
Conductor (copper)	mm^2	$22.5 \times 25.0, \varnothing 3.5$	$8.4 \times 8.4, \varnothing 2.5$	
Turns		7	10	
Current density, $t\bar{t}$	$A_{\text{RMS}}\text{mm}^{-2}$	2.0	5.0	4.7
Magnetic efficiency		> 0.92	> 0.98	
Temperature rise (7 bar)	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	9.4	26	8.2
Active mass (coils and yoke)	kg	2150	614	312
Coil overhang	mm	140	50	

Fig. 21: Field map in the yoke of the baseline quadrupole magnet (left) and of the sextupole magnet (right) at $t\bar{t}$ energy. The calculations were performed with FEMM software.

easing the installation and maintenance while also minimizing cost. This study is being conducted in the scope of the “FCC-ee Arc Half Cell Mock-up project”, and of the FCC-ee design study, elements of the arc cell are planned to be studied in a full-scale mock-up.

6.1 Booster and collider placement

The placement of the booster and the collider must be optimised in the radial and vertical directions of the tunnel cross-section, with a hard constraint of a maximum tunnel diameter of 5.5 m, as well as in the azimuthal direction. For what concerns the tunnel cross section, as also explained in [15], an optimized configuration with respect to those presented in [1] consists in placing the booster on top of the collider. This frees more space for the services, especially the cooling and ventilation piping, the transport vehicles, and the alignment system (Fig. 22).

On top of being more compact, the vertical configuration provides further advantages:

- Permitting smaller tunnel diameters in the RF sections.
- Same basement configuration as FCC-hh.
- Easier access for handling and removal of booster magnets and SSS.
- Better from radiation point of view, as the highest dose is generated on the outer side of the tunnel, and this could be detrimental to the booster ring in case of a horizontal placement [16].

Fig. 22: Configurations for the relative placement between booster and collider. Left: horizontal configuration. Right: vertical configuration.

However, the vertical positioning of the booster could raise dynamic stability challenges: due to the longer lever arm between the ground and the magnet, the booster could oscillate further, exceeding the tight dynamic positioning tolerances, particularly in the SSS region. For this reason, a significant effort in design and simulations is being made to improve the supporting system and maximize the stability of the two accelerators.

Given that the booster will be positioned above the collider, it is essential to maintain a sufficient clearance with the collider underneath. This could be done by azimuthally shifting the SSS of the collider with respect to the SSS of the booster, keeping the cell periodicity (i.e. the azimuthal distance between the booster SSS and the collider SSS is maintained constant along the ring). In fact, the SSS is the bulkiest section of the arc for both machines. With the proposed modification, the SSS of the collider will be positioned, azimuthally, in correspondence with the small and compact booster dipoles, and vice versa (Fig. 23).

Fig. 23: Azimuthal shift between booster and collider.

6.2 Optimisation of the booster supporting structure

Fig. 24 shows the current 3D model of an arc half-cell, focused on the short straight section of the collider and booster. It should be noted that these designs are constantly evolving and being optimized.

The supporting structures of the collider and the booster are being optimized structurally and in terms of stability. A Finite Element Method (FEM) has been defined and is described in the following steps:

1. Definition of a baseline model (support and simplified magnets);
2. Carry out static analysis of the system → assess the structural resistance and the static stability of the support;
3. Carry out modal analysis → assess the rigidity of the system, study the dynamic characteristics of the system;

Fig. 24: CAD model of an arc half-cell, with focus on the Short Straight Section.

4. Identify the transfer function of the support from the ground to the magnet axis → identify the support's critical modes, carry out a comparative study between different supports;
5. Conduct random vibration analysis in response to ground motion → study the impact of the support on the RMS at the magnetic centre, and obtain an estimate of this RMS;
6. Add vibrational cross-talk between the booster and the collider, add excitation forces dependent on the support environment such as pumps, water pipes, ventilation, etc.;
7. Compare the results to the specifications.

For the moment, this methodology is being applied from step 1 to step 5. Indeed, the vibrational cross-talk between the booster and the collider and how to account for it in the simulations is currently being studied. Further investigations are required to determine and include excitation forces.

This methodology was applied to the three geometries shown in Fig. 25 in order to compare their structural performance. Geometries 1 and 2 are fixed at ground level, the difference being in the offset between the centre of the collider and the booster. However, geometry 3 is fixed directly to the ceiling.

Fig. 25: Illustration of the alternative geometries tested for the booster support.

As shown in Table 15, geometry 2 has larger modes in the vertical direction than the other two geometries. The transfer functions of geometries 1 and 3 are similar except that, as can be seen in the graph on the left of Fig. 26, the first mode of geometry 3 has the highest gain for the first mode, i.e. 250% higher than that of geometry 1. In the horizontal direction, the first mode of geometry 3 is much weaker and is characterised by a pendulum-like movement of the platform. Hence, geometry 3 hanging from the ceiling is not recommended in terms of stability, compared to geometries fixed on the floor.

	Deflection	Mode shapes results			
		1 st vertical	2 nd vertical	1 st horizontal	2 nd horizontal
1: Centered with collider	0.46 mm	21 Hz	34 Hz	18 Hz	21 Hz
2: Shifted from Collider	0.19 mm	26 Hz	26 Hz	26 Hz	26 Hz
3: Ceiling	0.72 mm	21 Hz	50 Hz	13 Hz	31 Hz

Table 15: Summary table of results for these three geometries.

Fig. 26: Summary graphs of results for the three considered geometries (see Table 15). Top: Vertical request. Bottom: Horizontal request

Knowing the transfer function of the supporting structure between the ground and the centre of the magnet, it becomes possible to conduct random vibration analysis in response to ground motion. The dynamic properties of the ground in the FCC tunnel are not yet known, so the ground displacements (Power Spectral Density PSD) measured in the LHC tunnel [17] have been used to obtain first results. The PSD of the magnetic axis is computed as an output and then the integrated Root Mean Square (RMS) displacements at the level of this axis are computed. The methodology is explained in the Fig. 27. However, it is important to note that many assumptions have been made so far, such as the ground motion input, simplified magnets and interfaces (ground-support, support-magnets, etc.). The aim is therefore to benchmark these simulations using an experimental campaign. This experimental campaign consists of a 2.5 m-long Short Straight Section demonstrator allowing to understand how the different elements of the SSS affect stability. Step

by step the different elements will be characterised by experimental modal analysis and transfer function measurements. The experimental results will then be compared with simulations, with the aim of gradually refining the simulations to determine more accurately the dynamic stability of the different supports.

Fig. 27: Methodology of the dynamic stability analysis of the booster support.

The actual design is a compromise between an optimised design in terms of structural and stability aspects and all the limiting factors such as integration, safety, cost, manufacturing, etc. The optimisation is still ongoing and evolving, and other types of geometries are currently being evaluated.

7 RF systems

Since the CDR, the base design of the RF frequency has changed from 400 MHz to 800 MHz, requiring a revision of the total voltage budget. Assuming no energy gain ($E_{\text{gain}} = 0$) at injection and extraction, one can calculate the resulting RF voltage using the Eq (4):

$$V_{RF} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{C\lambda_{RF}\sigma_e^2 E_t \eta}{2\pi\sigma_z^2 \beta^3}\right)^2 + (E_{\text{gain}} + U_0)^2} \quad (4)$$

In this equation, C is the booster circumference, σ_z the bunch length, E_t the total energy, $\eta \simeq -\alpha_c$ the slippage factor, β the normalized velocity, λ_{RF} the RF cavities wavelength, U_0 the synchrotron energy loss per turn, and σ_e the energy spread.

At injection energy, the momentum acceptance is taken as a criterion for the calculation of the cavities RF voltage budget by solving Eq. (5):

$$\delta_p = \frac{2Q_s(V_{RF})\lambda_{RF}}{C\alpha_c} \sqrt{1 + \tan \phi_s(V_{RF}) \left(\phi_s(V_{RF}) - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)} \quad (5)$$

with $Q_s(V_{RF})$ the synchronous tune and $\phi_s(V_{RF})$ the synchronous phase.

Table 3 gives the required total voltages at injection and extraction with the momentum acceptance as a criterion. An extra voltage is required to include the energy gain during the ramp.

The RF system of the high energy booster will be installed in point L. It shall deliver a total RF voltage varying from about 80 MV at the Z pole to 10.2 GV at the $t\bar{t}$ energy, with an average beam current decreasing from 14.3 mA to 0.3 mA. The cavities will be installed gradually in the tunnel depending on the required beam energy. Considering four cavities per cryomodule, the total number of cryomodules to be installed is 135, which represents 38 % of the total number of cryomodules needed in the FCCee accelerator complex.

It is proposed to use the same 5-cell 800 MHz elliptical cavities as the one designed for the collider at the $t\bar{t}$ mode. As a baseline, the cavity manufacturing technology is the standard bulk niobium technology with a limitation of the usable accelerating gradient to 20 MV m^{-1} in operation, taking into account the fact that the cavities are qualified in a vertical cryostat at 20 % higher gradient and Q_0 . With an accelerating gradient of 20 MV m^{-1} the peak surface magnetic and electric fields are respectively 87.3 mT and 41.3 MV m^{-1} , which should give enough margin from quenching and electronic field emission thresholds. An alternative RF design has been studied with the goal to suppress longitudinal higher order modes and the need of a longitudinal feedback system against coupled bunch instabilities. However this design increases the magnetic and electric surface fields by respectively 18.5 % and 12.7 % is discarded for now. Another option consists in considering 6-cell cavities instead of 5-cell. By adding one cell the accelerating length is increased by 20 % and allows to save 20 CM in total. Trapped modes in the 4-cavity string module shall be carefully checked as well as the compatibility of with present SRF infrastructures (the 6-cell version is 1.5 m long from flange to flange).

A preliminary 3D mechanical model of the 800 MHz cavity with helium vessel is shown in Fig. 28.

Fig. 28: Preliminary mechanical design of the 800 MHz cavity equipped with its helium vessel.

The maximum RF peak power per cavity delivered to the beam is 100 kW to 150 kW when operating at the optimal frequency detuning and near the optimal loaded quality factor which is in the order of $Q_L = 1 \times 10^6$ to 20×10^6 . It is planned to use the same Fundamental Power Coupler (FPC) with variable coupling as the 200 kW CW FPC developed for the collider at the $t\bar{t}$ mode.

The development of a frequency tuning system able to operate in pulsed regime (flat top of 100 ms) with a resolution at the Hz level will be mandatory. It can be based on the elastic axial deformation of the cells by an electromechanical system equipped with a stepper motor and a piezo-electric actuator. New type of tuning technology can also be considered (for example a non-mechanical tuner using ferroelectric materials).

Different surface treatment recipes like mid-T bake or Nitrogen doping will be explored to reach a quality factor of $Q_0 = 3 \times 10^{10}$ at high field, leading to dynamic losses of about 20 W per cavity at 2 Kelvin. Alternative technologies like Nb on copper or Nb3Sn thin film coatings will be explored in a dedicated research program to reduce the investment and operational costs of the RF systems.

Concerning the RF power sources, 50 kW recombined Inductive Output Tubes (IOTs) will power each cavity at the $Z/W/H$ mode. The number of tubes to be recombined will depend on the required RF power overhead. At the $t\bar{t}$ mode where 10 kW to 20 kW per cavity is needed, solid state amplifiers are being envisaged.

8 Correction and tolerances

8.1 Correction strategy

The orbit correction procedure is divided in two sections: one with the sextupoles turned off (or very low strength) and the other with the sextupoles turned on (full strength). This decomposition sextupoles off/on of the orbit study is commonly done in accelerators such as SuperKEKB during commissioning [18]. We assume that all the orbit correctors of the Booster are individually powered, and they are placed at each quadrupole together with the BPM. Firstly, the sextupoles are off. We apply a correction, Segment-by-Segment (SbS) *i.e.* in our case, arc by arc; which is similar to the LHC commissioning [19]. After the SbS, two iterations of Singular Value Decompositions (SVD) are made on all arcs and in line, in order to reduce the residual orbit. This is sufficient to get an orbit reduced enough to find the closed orbit. After this step, multiple iterations of SVD in ring are made. Finally, the sextupoles are turned on and we do one iteration of SVD in ring. The tunes and the chromaticity are matched to nominal values, using the quadrupoles and sextupoles in the dispersion suppression and matching regions. Finally, one iteration of the orbit correction, tune and chromaticity is repeated.

We studied and tested different case scenarios on 100 seeds. The errors are reported in Table 16. We consider 200 μm mis-alignment from one girder to the other (about 25 m distance) and 50 μm mis-alignment for the elements placed on top of the girder (BPM, Quadrupole and orbit correctors).

Table 16: Summary of the different error types and their values. The girder to girder mis-alignment is 200 μm

Error type (Gaussian RMS)	Value	Unit
MB relative field error	10^{-3}	
MB main dipole roll error	300	μrad
MQ offset (with respect to the girder)	50	μm
MQ roll	100	μrad
MS offset (with respect to the girder)	50	μm
BPM offset (with respect to the girder)	50	μm
BPM resolution	50	μm
Girder-to-girder offset	200	μm

It is worth noticing that all the errors applied on the elements are randomly Gaussian distributed within ± 3 RMS.

8.2 Residual orbit and required dipole correctors

Figure 29 shows the RMS values of the residual orbit for the 100 different configurations of errors for the two iterations of the correction procedure described in the previous section. The RMS values for each of the error configuration are distributed around the dashed red line representing one analytical RMS estimate. The blue dots represent the values after one iteration of the full procedure described in the previous section, while the orange dots show the results after the second iteration. Both optics have similar final residual orbit values, even though in the case of the HFD optics, the results are less spread out.

The rms values of the correctors' strength for the same 100 different configurations are shown in Fig. 30. As for the residual orbit both optics have similar rms correctors' strength values.

Fig. 29: RMS values of the residual orbit for the 100 different error configurations described in the text. The results for the FODO and HFD lattice are shown on the left and right panel, respectively.

Fig. 30: RMS values of the correctors strength for the 100 different error configurations described in the text. The results for the FODO and HFD lattice are shown on the left and right panel, respectively.

Table 17: Average rms residual orbit and maximum rms corrector strength values after correction for 100 different error configurations based on table 16.

	Plane			3×RMS	
				Analytic	Seeds
Residual orbit	[μm]	x	FODO	252	171
			HFD	251	156
	y	FODO	253	163	
		HFD	253	156	
Corrector strength	[mT m]	x	FODO	23	24
			HFD	-	24
	y	FODO	22	24	
		HFD	-	24	

The average values of the rms residual orbit and of the maximum corrector strength are reported in Table 17.

8.3 Emittance evaluation

Following the correction of the closed orbit, the simulation of the emittance after the two iterations of correction is made to define the eventual need for a dedicated correction. This is made for the 100 corrected configurations depicted in the previous subsection at a beam energy of 45.6 GeV. We computed the emittance normalized to the natural emittance in the horizontal transverse plane, and normalized to the target vertical emittance obtained *via* the product of the natural horizontal emittance and the target coupling factor.

As seen in the Fig 31, the simulation shows an important value of the relative emittance in vertical transverse plane very strongly coupled ($\simeq 100\%$) to a very volatile behavior in horizontal transverse plane in both lattices. One can also consider that the HFD lattice seems to be more stable. The important values present in the vertical emittance plots are due to the target coupling factor

Fig. 31: Value of the normalized emittance after the 2 cycles of orbit correction. The results for the FODO and HFD lattice are shown on the left and right panel, respectively.

These values of the emittance and the apparent strong coupling between the two transverse planes call for dedicated correction to achieve the target extraction emittance in both transverse planes.

9 Booster operation

9.1 Filling scheme

The CDR scheme was based on Linac producing 2 bunches (25 ns spacing) at 200 Hz for the Z operation. The damping ring was running at 1.54 GeV and used for positrons only. The injection into the damping ring was staggered with a storage time of 42.5 ms corresponding to 4 damping times. The extraction was also staggered (first in first out). A timeline of the pulses in the damping ring is shown in Fig. 32 (left).

After the mid-term review, a new proposal is to produce and accelerate 4 pulses in the Linac with a spacing of 25 ns and a repetition frequency of 100 Hz. The damping ring is now running at 2.86 GeV and is used for both electrons and positrons. A timeline in the damping ring is shown for this new proposal in Fig. 32 (right).

Fig. 32: Pulse structure in the damping ring before injection into the linac of 20 GeV in the case of an operating frequency of 200 Hz (left) or 100 Hz (right).

The new scheme proposes also to transfer from the booster to the collider one tenth of the total number of bunches. A smaller number of bunches in each booster cycle has several advantages:

- Machine protection considerations only allow for about 1/10th of all bunches, i.e. 1120 (each with max. 1/10th of nominal collider bunch intensity) injected into collider at once at Z energy.
- Shorter booster injection plateau relaxes the required vacuum quality for tolerable emittance growth from rest gas collisions, and reduces the impact of Intra-Beam Scattering (IBS) and thus emittance growth on early injected bunches.
- Allows to distribute bunches along booster circumference. That relaxes the fast beam ion instability and tune shifts for electron beam, and the required RF power for beam loading compensation. This distribution can also be exploited to optimize filling of collider to mitigate e-cloud for positrons.
- Smaller variation of average luminosity of all bunches.
- Allows for faster reaction time for topping up critical bunches in case needed.

However, the main disadvantage is to increase the number of ramps and thus to affect the time required for top-up of all bunches (“effective cycle length”) as shown in Fig. 33. In the new scheme, we aim at at 1/10th of all bunches in each booster cycle. To keep some operation margins, the total ramping time in the booster should be ~ 1 s at Z operation as summarized in Table 18.

An example of the filling pattern in the booster is shown in Fig. 34. It is worth noting that for the Z operation, it is possible to play on which subset of bunches is injected from the booster to the collider. Such a scheme provides flexibility in the accumulation phase of the collider to create gaps in the bunch train and possibly mitigate electron cloud.

Fig. 33: Effective cycle time as a function of the ramping time and the number of transferred bunches per booster cycle. The brown dot corresponds to the scheme in mid-term review and the blue one for the new scheme.

The three operation modes run with a smaller number of bunches and lower bunch intensity compared to Z . A low bunch intensity from injector needed ($< 1 \times 10^{10}$) resolves transverse coupled mode instabilities (TMCI) limitations in the booster (see Sec. 4). The three operation modes allow longer abort gaps, partly occupied by non-colliding bunches for energy calibration. There is still margin to reduce injection rate (i.e. pausing between cycles) for energy saving in top-up mode or increased booster cycle length (e.g. if beam injection in the collider needs to be done in chunks). Currently, for the WW operation, we are considering transferring half of bunches at each injection to limit the length of injection plateau. For the ZH and $t\bar{t}$ operation, one requirement on the filling scheme is to have always only one beam present in common RF section. The number of bunches is small enough to run injector complex at 50 Hz with 2 bunches.

Table 18: Filling parameters

		Z	WW	ZH	ttbar
Linac repetition rate	[Hz]	100	100	50	50
Bunches per Linac pulse		4	4	2	2
Linac bunch spacing	[ns]	25	25	25	25
Booster accumulation time	[s]	2.8	2.32	3.0	0.64
Booster total ramping time	[s]	1.0	1.6	2.6	4.3
Booster cycle length	[s]	3.8	3.92	5.6	4.94
Bunches per booster cycle		1120	928	300	64
Number of bunches in collider		11 200	1856	300	64
Max. bunch intensity injected in collider	10^{10}	2.15	1.0	1.0	1.0
Nominal bunch intensity in collider	10^{10}	21.5	13.8	16.9	14.8
Allowable charge imbalance	[%]	5	3	3	3
Beam lifetime: lumi 4 IPs, (q,BS,lattice)/4	[s]	916	517	428	497

Fig. 34: Filling pattern for the different operation modes (from top to bottom): Z , WW , ZH , and $t\bar{t}$.

9.2 Emittance evolution

The transverse damping time is respectively 9 s, 0.763 s, 0.141 s, 0.0419 s and 0.0119 s at the injection energy of 20 GeV and at the extraction energy of the 4 operating modes. The direct consequence is that the damping time at Z operation is of the same order of magnitude as the total ramping time given in Table 18 whereas the damping time is small for the other modes. Therefore, the emittance and energy spread at the extraction at the Z mode will depend on the initial injection parameters whereas the equilibrium emittance will be reached for the other modes. That is why we have only considered the Z mode to evaluate if the extracted emittance stays within the injection tolerances to the collider. In this study, we have considered 2 injection cases:

Case 1 (Linac alone of 20 GeV) $\epsilon_x = 10 \mu\text{m} \times \epsilon_y = 10 \mu\text{m} \times \sigma_\delta = 1 \times 10^{-3}$.

Case 2 (High-energy damping ring) $\epsilon_x = 20 \mu\text{m} \times \epsilon_y = 2 \mu\text{m} \times \sigma_\delta = 1 \times 10^{-3}$

The equilibrium emittance in the collider at Z operation is $\epsilon_{x,\text{RMS}} = 0.71 \text{ nm} \times \epsilon_{y,\text{RMS}} = 1.9 \text{ pm} \times \sigma_\delta = 1.09 \times 10^{-3}$. A first study on the injection into the collider suggests that the collider can accept up to twice larger horizontal emittance and 5 times larger vertical emittance. That is why the target for the emittance at extraction is $\epsilon_{x,\text{target}} = 1.42 \text{ nm} \times \epsilon_{y,\text{target}} = 9.4 \text{ pm}$.

The baseline energy ramp considers a parabolic increase from 0 GeV s^{-1} to 80 GeV s^{-1} , a linear ramp up to a maximum energy higher than the extraction one (to speed-up the radiation damping), a decrease of the extraction energy, a flat-top, and finally a ramp-down of the magnets. The current total time of the booster ramp is 1.14 s, near the target of 1 s and can be shared between a ramp-up of 0.706 s, a flat-top of 0.1 s, and a ramp-down of 0.334 s. That is worth noting that we consider the same maximum slope for the magnetic field in the dipole in the ramp-up and ramp-down. However, it is likely to be able to have a faster ramp-down since no beam is circulating at this time. The stability constraints and beam loading in the RF cavities are not a concern during the ramp-down.

The evolutions of the beam energy, of the radiated power, of the minimum RF voltage, of the horizontal and vertical RMS emittance, and of the energy spread are given in Fig. 35 for the baseline. The maximum energy brought by the cavities per turn is then 90.6 MeV/turn . In the case 1, the final vertical RMS emittance is 30 pm well above the target of 9.4 pm . In the case 2, the final vertical RMS emittance is 6.12 pm , which is above the equilibrium emittance in the collider but within the injection acceptance.

If the ramp does not include an energy overshoot but keeps the same up-ramp, flat-top, down-ramp times and a parabolic shape, the maximum energy brought by the cavities per turn is reduced to 51.7 MeV/turn . The final vertical RMS emittance becomes respectively for both cases 55.4 pm and 11.2 pm well above the target of 9.4 pm . We clearly see the interest to go to higher energies to accelerate the damping and go to lower energies. We have evaluated some mitigation solutions to be able to speed-up the damping during the ramp and to get a smaller vertical emittance by keeping a total ramping time of 1.14 s. In all cases, accelerating the damping implies to increase the radiated power and thus the required cavity voltage.

We propose three solutions to get a final smaller vertical emittance. The first possibility is to increase the allocated time of the ramp-up by decreasing the time of the ramp-down. For instance, if the ramp-down decreases by 170 ms, the time of the ramp-up becomes 876 ms. That enables also to go to a higher maximum energy and thus to accelerate the damping with an increased power consumption. The maximum energy brought by the cavities per turn is then 130.0 MeV/turn . The final vertical RMS emittance for both cases is respectively 9.27 pm and 1.99 pm . The second possibility is to go to higher energy by increasing the slope of the magnetic field from 80 GeV s^{-1} to 100 GeV s^{-1} for instance. The maximum energy brought by the cavities per turn is then 158.5 MeV/turn . The final vertical RMS emittance for both cases is respectively 9.1 pm and 1.96 pm . Finally, the last proposal is to insert a wiggler in one of the straight sections. For the exercise, we have considered $n_W = 1$ wiggler of 4.925 m with $n_P = 43$ poles of length $L_P = 95 \text{ mm}$ each, a field in the gap of $B_W = 1.45 \text{ T}$, a gap between the poles of 20 mm . The parameters of the wiggler are very preliminary and need to be consolidated. The aim was to have an order of magnitude of what is needed. The change of the second synchrotron integrate \mathcal{I}_ϵ is given by:

$$\Delta \mathcal{I}_2 \approx n_W (n_P - 2) L_P \left(\frac{\epsilon B}{p} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

The parameters of the wiggler were calculated to go from $\mathcal{I}_2 = 0.59 \text{ mm}^{-1}$ to $\mathcal{I}_2 = 2.43 \text{ mm}^{-1}$ at injection energy of 20 GeV . The evolution of the beam energy, voltage, and beam emittance with an additional wiggler is given in Fig. 35. The emittance evolution takes into account that \mathcal{I}_ϵ is varying with time since we assume a constant magnetic field in the wiggler. The maximum energy brought by the cavities per turn is then 122.5 MeV/turn . The final vertical RMS emittance for both cases is respectively 8.74 pm and 1.84 pm .

To conclude, the baseline enables to reach a final vertical emittance within the requirements only if a high-energy damping ring is used and that is possible to keep a normalized vertical emittance of 2 pm by going through the linac. However, at the price of more RF power, it is possible to get the target vertical emittance with a ramp of 1 s if it is possible to combine a smaller ramp-down and a wiggler. Increasing the acceleration to reach higher energies more quickly can be beneficial, but caution is needed to avoid excessively high energies; otherwise, the radiated power will increase significantly, leading to high power consumption.

Fig. 35: Evolution of the beam energy (first line), of the radiated power and required RF voltage (second line), of the horizontal RMS emittance (third line), vertical RMS emittance (fourth line), RMS energy spread (last line) as a function of time for the baseline parameters.

9.3 Ramping strategy

Following an accumulation time, the booster will ramp the beam energy from the injection energy (20 GeV) up to extraction energy (45.6 GeV for Z , 182.5 GeV for $t\bar{t}$). The optimisation strategy has to ensure beam stability and reach the target emittances.

- The start of the ramp shall be adiabatic to avoid shocking the bunch.
- The energy gain per turn is limited by Eddy currents in the magnets. A conservative approach considers a maximum of 80 GeV/s.
- When approaching high energies, the energy gain is dominated by the energy provided to compensate losses due to synchrotron radiation. The extraction energy needs to be reached adiabatically.

The tracking simulation suite BLoND [20] was used to design the energy and RF voltage ramps for all four modes. The next subsections detail the energy ramps of the two extreme modes (the high current mode Z and the high energy mode $t\bar{t}$).

Z mode ramp

In order to reach the target emittances required by the collider (see subsection 9.2), the ramping strategy considers an energy overshoot up to 53 GeV. Because the energy lost due to synchrotron radiation scales as the fourth power of the energy, the 8 GeV excess needs to be compensated by a high RF voltage.

In order to design the voltage ramp, we consider the phase-space longitudinal stability regions at the three extreme regimes: flat bottom, overshoot maximum and flat top, see Fig. 37. In order

Fig. 36: Evolution of the beam energy (first line), of the radiated power and required RF voltage (second line), of the horizontal RMS emittance (third line), vertical RMS emittance (fourth line), RMS energy spread (last line) as a function of time for the baseline parameters and the addition of a wiggler of 4.925 m, 43 50 mm long poles with a gap of 20 mm, a gap field of 1.45 m.

to keep the filling fraction small enough (ratio of bunch emittance and stability area), one needs at least 85 MV of RF voltage.

Fig. 37: Longitudinal phase space stability regions delimited by the separatrix (red curve). Blue lines show curves of constant energy. Left panel corresponds to flat bottom, with an energy $E = 20$ GeV and voltage $V_{\text{RF}} = 50.1$ MV. Right panel corresponds to flat top, with an energy $E = 45.6$ GeV and voltage $V_{\text{RF}} = 57.2$ MV. The middle panel corresponds to the maximum of the energy overshoot, $E = 53$ GeV, with voltage $V_{\text{RF}} = 85$ MV.

We propose a doubly parabolic voltage ramp up to 85 MV, see Fig. 38. The start is parabolic for the first 1% voltage gain to avoid shocking the bunch, then a steep linear part, and a parabolic curve for the remaining 20% of the voltage increase. From 85 MV, the voltage is ramped down to 57.2 MV with a similar strategy, parabolic for the initial 20%, then linear, then parabolic for the

remaining 40 %, before a 0.1 s flat top. The RF-based optimised proposed ramp shall be fine-tuned with hardware considerations.

Fig. 38: Left: Energy and voltage ramping strategies for the Z mode. The total energy gain is plotted as a full green line, it is the sum of the energy gain needed for acceleration (light-blue dashed line) and the energy required to compensate synchrotron radiation losses (dark blue dashed line). The voltage is shown as a full orange line. Right: Synchronous phase, theoretical (full blue line) against simulated bunch position (dotted orange line).

$t\bar{t}$ mode ramp

The $t\bar{t}$ mode ramp lasts 2.03 s, corresponding to 6713 turns in the booster ring, followed by a 0.1 s flat top. The energy increases nine-fold, from 20 GeV to 182.5 GeV. At flat top, the energy loss due to synchrotron radiation is substantial (over 10 GeV/turn). The top energy has to be reached as slowly as possible. The proposed energy and voltage ramps are shown in Fig. 39. We propose a preliminary solution with a linear voltage increase from 50.1 MV up to 11.533 GV.

Fig. 39: Left: Energy and voltage ramping strategies for the $t\bar{t}$ mode. The total energy gain is plotted as a full green line, it is the sum of the energy gain needed for acceleration (light-blue dashed line) and the energy required to compensate synchrotron radiation losses (dark blue dashed line). The voltage is shown as a full orange line. Right: Synchronous phase, theoretical (full blue line) against simulated bunch position (dotted orange line).

10 Booster radiation and shielding

10.1 Introduction

The generation of synchrotron radiation by the electron and positron beams can have a significant impact on machine components and other equipment in the tunnel. This requires a careful study of radiation levels and associated radiation effects. The radiation fields generated by synchrotron photons can, for example, affect the lifetime of equipment due to cumulative radiation damage in equipment components. The main concern in FCC-ee is the total ionising dose in electronics and organic materials, such as busbar insulation, cables, optical fibers, seals, etc. As already observed in LEP, the ionizing dose can severely affect the organic insulation of magnet coils and cables, and can rapidly darken optical fibres [21]. Besides the ionizing dose, other instantaneous and cumulative radiation effects also require a thorough assessment. These include radiation-induced heating, single event effects in electronics, atomic displacements, and radiation-induced corrosion. Single-event effects can, for example, lead to premature beam aborts and can hence perturb the machine availability. On the other hand, radiolysis of humid air can lead to the production of nitric acids, which can lead to the corrosion of metals.

Considering the significant power dissipated by synchrotron photons in FCC-ee, suitable mitigation measures have to be developed in order to avoid radiation-induced equipment failures and a degraded machine performance. Although the radiated power is much higher in the collider ring than in the booster, the contribution of the latter still has to be assessed carefully. In this section, we study the ionizing dose generated by synchrotron photon emission in the booster arcs and evaluate the shielding efficiency of the dipole yokes. Other radiation effects, like single event upsets or radiation-induced corrosion, are out of the scope of the present contribution and will be addressed in future studies. Nevertheless, the presented dose studies provide already a first assessment of the shielding requirements for the booster.

10.2 Synchrotron radiation power during booster cycle

The energy loss because of synchrotron photon emission increases steeply with the beam energy ($\propto E^4/(m^4\rho)$) and is a significant concern in circular electron-positron colliders because of the small particle mass. Hence, a large bending radius ρ is essential for a high-intensity machine like the FCC-ee; ρ is about 10 km for the collider and booster, which is about three times larger than in LEP. Besides the increasing power radiated at higher beam energies, the radiation levels in the tunnel environment are more pronounced at higher E since the emitted photons become more penetrating. Radiation-induced effects will hence be dominated by the $t\bar{t}$ operation mode (182.5 GeV). A key figure is the critical energy, $E_c \propto E^3/\rho$, which divides the photon spectrum in two parts of equal power emission. For a bending radius of 10 km, the critical energy is 0.02 MeV at Z -pole (45.6 GeV), but increases to 1.3 MeV in $t\bar{t}$ operation.

The main source of radiation in the FCC-ee arcs is the synchrotron radiation produced in the collider ring, which is limited by design to 100 MW for all operation modes (50 MW/beam). The synchrotron power emitted during booster cycles is much lower due to the lower stored beam intensity, but still requires a careful assessment since no dedicated photon stoppers are foreseen like in the collider ring. The radiated power and photon spectra depend on the evolution of the beam energy during a booster cycle. Figure 40 shows the time dependence of the beam energy, critical energy and emitted power during a booster ramp from 20 GeV to 182.5 GeV ($t\bar{t}$ operation). The figure assumes a bunch train of 56 bunches, with a bunch intensity of $10^{10} e^\pm$ (see Table 3). At the end of the ramp, the power reaches almost 3 MW, while the average power during the ~ 2 s-long ramp is about 1 MW. The repetition rate of booster cycles for $t\bar{t}$ operation is about 10 s, alternating between electrons and positrons. Taking into account the time without beam between cycles, the average power is less than 0.2 MW, i.e., more than 500 times less than in the collider. For other beam modes, the emitted power is even less due to the lower flattop energy.

Fig. 40: Time evolution of the beam energy (top), critical energy (center) and emitted synchrotron radiation power (bottom) for a booster ramp from 20 GeV to 182.5 GeV ($t\bar{t}$ operation). The flat bottom and flat top plateaus are not shown.

10.3 Ionizing dose in tunnel

Considering the significant challenge posed by synchrotron radiation emitted in the collider ring, it is highly desirable that the booster contribution to the ionizing dose in the tunnel remains as low as reasonably achievable. The radiation shielding approaches differ between collider and booster, due to the different magnet and vacuum system design. The vacuum system of the collider incorporates localised photon stoppers made of a copper alloy (CuCrZr), which are placed in the winglets of the vacuum chamber and directly intercept the synchrotron radiation fan [22, 23]. At higher energies, the radiation leakage from these stoppers becomes significant, which requires the integration of additional shielding elements into the collider dipoles. A first conceptual design of the collider shielding configuration has been developed recently [24], but requires further optimization. Contrary to the collider, no photon stoppers are foreseen in the booster and the synchrotron photons impact directly on the vacuum chamber. While the chamber walls are too thin to fully shield the photons and secondary particles, the O-shaped yokes of the booster dipoles provide nevertheless a significant attenuation of the radiation penetrating the chamber walls. The required shielding efficiency of the booster dipole yokes provides an important input for the magnet design.

In order to estimate the cumulative ionizing dose in the tunnel, FLUKA Monte Carlo simulations [25–27] were performed for both the collider and booster. Figure 41 presents annual dose estimates for the tunnel cross section ($t\bar{t}$ mode). The simulation assumes 185 days of operation, with 75% machine uptime. The results for the collider include a 60 cm-long Pb shielding around the photon stoppers, with a thickness of 10 cm on the internal and external side of the magnets. For the booster, dipole iron yokes with a thickness of 2 cm and 4 cm were simulated. The simulation results in Fig. 41 demonstrate that, with the present collider shielding, the dose contribution

Fig. 41: Annual ionizing dose in the tunnel ($t\bar{t}$ operation), showing separately the contributions of the collider (left) and the booster (middle: with a 2 cm-thick yoke, right: with a 4 cm-thick yoke). The collider simulations assume a preliminary lead shielding around discrete photon stoppers (10 cm on the horizontal plane). The studies were carried out with the FLUKA code. The FLUKA magnet models are shown at the top of the figure.

of the collider dominates. At the location of cable trays, which are installed on the walls (>2 m above floor level), the dose due to collider operation reaches 10 kGy/year to 40 kGy/year, while the booster contributes a few kGy/year if the dipole yoke is 2 cm thick. Anticipating a further improvement of the collider shielding configuration, with the goal to reduce the dose at cable trays to less than 10 kGy/year, the contribution of the booster cannot be neglected. It is hence desirable to reduce the booster-induced dose at the walls to less than 1 kGy/year, which can be achieved by increasing the yoke thickness of booster dipoles to 4 cm.

The presented results demonstrate that the contribution of the booster to the overall dose levels in the tunnel has to be studied in conjunction with the collider shielding. Further studies are needed, both for the collider and booster, in order to optimize the overall shielding strategy. Different components can show a different sensitivity to radiation, which needs to be accounted for in the required shielding efficiency. For example, organic insulation of standard cables can typically sustain of the order of 100 kGy, whereas electronics based on commercial-off-the-shelf components can typically not withstand levels above 1 kGy. Finding a compromise between suitable shielding solutions and a radiation-hard component and equipment design is essential for the FCC-ee, in order to avoid radiation-induced equipment failures or a degradation of the collider performance.

11 Conclusion and perspectives

Since the CDR, the booster has faced several major changes:

- The layout has changed to follow the different changes on the collider layout (see Sec. 1.3: the circumference has decreased; the length of the insertions has changed to go from a scheme with 2 IPs to 4 IPs; the booster is located in top of the collider with a transverse offset in the arcs; the location of the RF cavities has moved.
- The optics is still based on FODO cells (see Sec. 2.2 but the parameter review pushed to maintain the same optics for the different operation modes to reduce the costs. An alternative, based on hybrid cell (see Sec. 2.3;), has been proposed and compared. The matching conditions, including

second-order considerations, have been improved and enlarged the momentum acceptance and dynamic aperture.

- The injection and extraction systems have been developed. The placement of the transfer lines from the pre-injector complex to the booster has been optimised (see Sec. 3.1). The extraction and dump lines are located in section B (see Sec.3.2). A baseline of the injection and extraction sections exists. The baseline injection scheme requires a slight modification of one arc cell. The injection and extraction sections are able to transport the required envelopes of the circulating and injected/extracted beams. The machine protection at extraction is highly challenging due to the high stored energy and has pushed to reduce the total number of bunches at Z and W operation. The required hardware for the injection, extraction, and dump have been listed.
- The collective effects (see Sec. 4) have been studied for the updated optics and considered different sources of instabilities: mismatching at injection, microwave, transverse mode coupling, transverse and longitudinal coupled bunches. The studies have shown that present baseline injection parameters from the high-energy LINAC allows for a significant margin to avoid mismatch and microwave instabilities at injection energy (see Sec. 4.2). Studies on the coupled bunch instabilities have shown that the new parameters (especially the reduced number of stored bunches at Z -operation and the enlarged beam pipe) relax the threshold (see Sec. 4.3). Nevertheless, a transverse damper (although with relaxed damping time) is still mandatory. Single bunch instabilities were investigated for Copper and stainless steel beam pipes of several diameters as well as for different values of momentum compaction. The analysis has pushed to take as a baseline a Copper beam pipe with a diameter of 60 mm. With such parameters and with only the beam pipe as an impedance contributor, the beam is stable for all operating modes with the baseline optics.
- A baseline design for the arc dipoles (see Sec 5.2), quadrupoles, and sextupoles (see Sec. 5.3) exists. The obtained field quality is within the requirements.
- Mechanical studies have shown that the optimum placement of the booster is on top of the collider (see Sec. 6.1). Numerical procedures have been developed to optimize the stability of the supporting structures. If the optimisation is still ongoing and evolving, it is already possible to compare different geometries and select the most promising.
- The frequency of the RF cavities in the booster is now 800 MHz against 400 MHz in the CDR (see Sec. 7). The installation strategy of the RF cavities from Z to $t\bar{t}$ has been accordingly updated. The baseline technology of the booster cavities is now similar to the one used for the $t\bar{t}$ operation in the collider. The RF power sources will be based on Inductive Output Tubes at the $Z/W/ZH$ modes. For $t\bar{t}$, solid state amplifiers are under investigation.
- The correction strategy has been improved and enables to relax the alignment tolerances (see Sec. 8.1). However, the studies have shown that the orbit correction is not sufficient and it is mandatory to have additional tuning schemes to keep the final emittance within the requirements.
- The filling scheme has been updated to take into account the new number of stored bunches in the booster (at Z operation it has been divided by a factor of about 10) and also the modified repetition frequency of the LINAC. The smaller number of bunches stored in the booster solves several issues but requires a faster booster effective cycle (see Sec. 9.1). A criteria to validate the booster cycle is the emittance and energy spread at extraction. The studies have shown that the bottleneck is the Z operation. The conclusion of this study is that it is possible to have a total cycle of the booster within the requirements if we combine several solutions among a shorter ramp-down, a higher energy during the ramp (and decelerate after) to speed-up the damping, an additional wiggler, and/or use of a high-energy damping ring to inject a smaller vertical emittance into the booster (see Sec. 9.2). Tracking studies have been performed to validate and optimise the ramping strategy (see Sec. 9.3).
- The synchrotron radiation power emitted from the booster during one cycle has been evaluated (see Sec. 10.2) to estimate the ionizing dose in tunnel (see Sec. 10.3). The studies have shown that the contribution of the booster to the overall dose levels in the tunnel has to be studied

in conjunction with the collider shielding. A recommendation is to increase the thickness of the booster dipole yokes from 20 mm to 40 mm to get a better shielding efficiency.

A lot of progress and changes were done on the booster since the CDR. The current booster performances fill most of the requirements. The baseline configuration of the booster enables to accept the beam coming from the injection complex for all operating modes. Indeed, the dynamic aperture, the momentum acceptance, and the threshold for the different beam instabilities are large enough. The optics for the injection and extraction enables to accept the envelopes of the injected, circulating, and extracted beams. The main hardware devices like the arc dipoles, quadrupoles, sextupoles, RF cavities seems to be technically feasible. The misalignment requirements are in the state-of-the-art. It seems to be possible to operate the booster with the required cycle for the filling and top-up operation of the collider. Nevertheless, there are still several remaining additional studies to fully validate the booster design. Among the different topics, we can cite the followings :

- Currently, the optics of the injection section is not yet integrated into the whole booster ring. An additional iteration is necessary to perform a second-order matching of these insertions to ensure that the dynamic aperture and momentum acceptance are not affected during injection. The placement of injection elements for the vertical injection scheme and threading of the injected beam through the lattice elements is particularly challenging. It is necessary to undergo detailed studies on the feasibility of the magnets and proposed channels for the injected beam. Some technical solutions are proposed for the septa and kickers and could be developed towards a technical design but could also benefit from further R&D to apply newer technologies. The apertures and strengths used in the extraction and dump baseline concept are capable of transporting the envelopes of the circulating and extracted beams, but a more detailed study, including kicker technology choices and filling scheme requirements, will be needed to finalise the requirements and converge on the technology choices. Despite the reduced beam intensity in the booster, such beams remain extremely critical and potentially destructive. Additional measures must be considered to ensure the safety and integrity of all machine components in case of a failure during the extraction and transfer processes. It is necessary to develop a dedicated system to monitor the position of the beam in the extraction and dump regions, to evaluate the required reaction time to detect anomalies and safely dispose of the beam, and to have interlocks to avoid drifts beyond well-defined limits.
- Collective effects studies suggest that we have a significant margin to avoid mismatching and microwave instabilities at injection energy. However, the studies with the jitter at injection need to be refined to include the anharmonicity of the optics. The TMCI and TCBI were evaluated with only the beam pipe as impedance contributors. If currently, the injected beam parameters are below the instability threshold, we need to refine the impedance budget and include all other contributors to make sure that the total impedance stays within the stability requirements. It is essential to note that the current collective effects studies are still preliminary. The next step is to perform self-consistent simulations, incorporating intra-beam scattering, wake-fields, and synchrotron radiation effects, for a thorough assessment of their impact on longitudinal and transverse motion during accumulation, ramp-up, and flat-top stages.
To go further and validate the booster dipole design, the next step is to produce and test a short prototype. The optimisation of the magnets will be pursued in order to include in the process (1) the yoke thickness of the dipole to provide additional radiation shielding, (2) the operation temperature of the magnets to improve the efficiency of waste heat recovery, (3) the industrialisation and design for manufacture and assembly, and (4) detailed integration with the other technical systems.

It is important to note that the simulation of the supporting structures includes many assumptions. The next step is to benchmark these simulations using an experimental campaign. The experimental results will then be compared with simulations, with the aim of gradually refining the simulations to determine more accurately the dynamic stability of the different supports.

In the future, it will be necessary to develop a frequency tuning system able to operate the RF cavities in pulsed regime (flat top of 100 ms) with a resolution at the Hz level. Different surface treatment recipes will be explored to reach a quality factor of $Q_0 \sim 3 \times 10^{10}$ at high field.

The tuning strategy is well defined for the orbit correction. The next steps are to add quadrupole correctors to perform the dispersion and coupling correction and be able to reach the target emittances despite machine imperfections.

There is still room for improvement in the ramp strategy. The next steps are to optimise the ramp shape (cryogenics and RF consumption, Eddy currents in the magnets) by keeping a total cycle time short enough for top-up operation in order to get the final emittance within the tolerances. To this stage, the main efforts concentrated on Z and $t\bar{t}$ operation. However, the other modes should benefit from similar optimisations.

The results presented demonstrate that the contribution of the booster to the overall dose levels in the tunnel must be studied in conjunction with the collider shielding. In the next steps, it will be mandatory to perform further investigations in order to optimize the overall shielding strategy.

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